

30 YEARS OF NANOSCIENCE AT BANAT UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES AND VETERINARY MEDICINE „King Mihai I of Romania” FROM TIMIȘOARA

1. Reflected in Different Publications

Gallia BUTNARU¹

Abstract. *In a short retrospective this paper presents the results and the important findings in the researches regarding Magnetic-Nanocomposites utilization at Banat University of Sciences (Anton, et al., 1988, Butnaru and Roosz, 1988). The paper brings attention to a pioneering research in the nanomagnetic materials field. We are briefly presenting the results of NMPs involvement with the plant's organogenesis and animal health as well as the environment protection. The researchers focused on a lot of questions and opened new domains of study but throughout the obtained results suitable application were formulated. The work resumes the results of 160 scientific works made by 291 researchers from all the Faculties of our University. It points out the interest for different topics, the improvement of producing bio-nanomaterials, their utilization and the visible results reflected in different publications.*

Keywords: 30 years of MNPs researches, publications, magnetic-nano materials, utilization.

Introduction

The staff of the Polytechnic University and the Romanian Academy, Timisoara Branch, developed a new class of materials of nano dimensions (Anton et al. 1977 and 1990). In the 1970s all over the world as well as in our country the perspective of their utilization was the industry. The idea of using them in biology was a utopia.

In our researches was introduced a new and particular topic the utilization of Romanian Nano-Materials in biology and agriculture, generally named now “agricultural nanotechnology”. About 10 years before our research (1959) Feynman mentioned: ...the biological example of writing information on a small scale has inspired me to think of something that should be possible. He understood how a “smaller organism” is capable to manage his energy for a better activity to survive in improper conditions. He has believed in.... “manipulating

¹ Banat University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine “King Mihai I of Romania” from Timișoara, e-mail: galliab@yahoo.com

and controlling things on a small scale”;which “would have an enormous number of technical applications”..... In “the marvellous biological system” he has seen a big hope (Feynman, 1959).

The first Magnetic Liquids (ML) prepared in Romania was obtained in Iasi at the Center of Technical Physics during 1970-1975 (Neaga and Lazar, 1987).

At the same time in Timisoara Prof. Anton I. PhD. organized the first lab to produce magnetic liquids for industry (1971). He was also the first initiator and the supporter for MNPs utilization in the bio domain. Due to his competence and his vision of the future our University was involved in the world pioneering research. Very soon the idea was taken into account by other Universities Research Centers which started to work with different types of Magnetic Liquids.

As new topic the name of the same product was changed several times. Thus at first was used the name “Magnetic Liquid” (ML), then “Ferrofluid” (FF), “Magnetic-Nanofluid” (MNF), etc. This is the reason why different research centres and authors used different names for the same product. The efficacy or “magnetization power” of the product is accounted in Gs units (cm³; Fe₃O₄/cm³).

The research centres involved in ML utilization in agriculture and biology were: Timisoara: Banat University of Agriculture, Faculty of Agriculture (1983) and the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine (1991); Bucharest: Research Center for Ecological Technology (1994); Craiova: Craiova University, Horticulture Faculty (1994); Arad: Vest University “Vasile Goldis” (2001); Oradea: Oradea University, Faculty of Biology (2004).

This study was structured per time periods and on interest areas.

The major goal was: to emphasize the studies with Magnetic-Nano Liquids to show the obtained results in important domains of agriculture. It was important to be established if the NMLs are useful to enhance the plant performances, would contribute to plant and animal as well as the environmental protection, or to prevent biotic and abiotic stress. Our problem was to establish the positive/negative effect of MNP on tissue, cell, and chromosome and if they are involved in the DNA structure and function.

Investigation details

Each researcher or person in charge of an experiment has chosen the biological material that was considered the most appropriate for the intended purpose. A large number of plants were used as biological material, economical important species as wheat, corn, triticale, potato, tomatoes as well as “model plants” *Arabidopsis thaliana* *Nicotiana tabaccum* and *Saintpaulia ionantha*. Lab and farm animals as well as company species were subjects of animal science and veterinary medicine experiments. *Drosophila melanogaster* was used as a model for chain of harmful insects and their entomophagous. Bacteria and fungi species were used to understand how the MNP acts in their life cycle.

Specific methods were applied to each group of the organism of interest to clarify the impact of MNP in their life cycle. The procedures of work have aimed to highlight the direct and indirect action of PM upon cell activity, in mitosis and in meiosis respectively and on chromosome chiasmata.

The electron microscope inquiry was used to point out the involvement of MNP with subcellular components.

The experimental regime was kept under control in the lab or growth chambers but was subject to external factors influence in field conditions. In both conditions was followed the relationship between magnetic liquids (ML) - magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) by one hand and plants - animals - insects and microorganisms on the other hand.

In all experiments the statistical analysis was applied (Ceapoiu, 1968, Ciulcă, 2006).

The data of this work present scientific results taken into account in publications, proceedings, PhD thesis, diploma papers, and symposiums, round tables or debates. In the graphs 1 to 6 are illustrated the main domains that had been followed at different time periods.

About the Magnetic Nano Liquids used

During the years special tailored magnetic nanomaterials were prepared depending on:

- nano – core:

Fe_3O_4 , $\gamma\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ and CoFe_2O_4 , $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 + \text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4$, and with Zn:Mn:Fe₃+

- stabilizers:

Group I produced in the 1980s was $\gamma \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 / \text{H}_2\text{O}$ or Dodecylbenzene Sulfonate (DBS);

Group II - $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 / \text{C}_4\text{OH}$ prepared between 1988 and 1990;

Group III Bio - produced during 1990-2000 - $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 / \text{Lauric Acid/DBS}$ ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{LA-DBS}$); lauric acid/lauric acid ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{LA-LA}$); lauric acid/citric acid ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{LA-CA}$); myristic acid/DBS ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{MA-DBS}$);

Group VI Bio – CoFe_2O_4 stabilized with oleic acid/DBS; myristic acid/DBS; lauric acid/citric acid; lauric acid /oleic acid;

Group V – Montmorillonite-clay complexes prepared in 2003 were:

montmorillonite $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{lauric acid}$ (bilayer); suspension of montmorillonite Fe_3O_4 and lauric acid; suspension of montmorillonite CoFe_2O_4 and lauric acid. - carriers:

- Aqueous: Water - FM/W (Doina Bica Patent RO-90078/85); “vine tears”

- LV; FM/LV/oleine; LV/lauric acid; (collected by us; LV have been used in traditional Romanian medicine); “depleted water” - DDW, FM/DDW/oleine; FM/DDW/lauric acid; (DDW prepared at the National Research and Development Institute for Cryogeny and Isotopic Technologies Rm. Vâlcea, Romania; DDW is used in cancer therapy);

- Oleous: Mineral oil - MO; Soya oil - FM/SO; (Doina Bica & Mirea Radu, Patent RO-93107/87); Sunflower oil - FM/SfO (Doina Bica et al, Patent RO-105049/1995);

- Lanoline FM was also prepared (Doina Bica et al, Patent RO-105048/1989).

The NMLs were prepared Center for Fundamental and Advanced Technical Research, the Romanian Academy, Timișoara Branch, by Chem Eng. Doina Bica, Ph.D. and were characterised by Phy. Ladislau Vekas, Ph.D., et al., 2001 from the National Center for Engineering of Systems with Complex Fluids, University Politehnica Timisoara.

Results

From 17 top journals of Nanoscience 52.9% are dedicated to medicine, 11.76% to biomaterials and only 35.34% for all other fields (biology, agriculture, environment, techniques of preparation, etc.). As in most cases, nanotechnology applications to the agricultural field are still relatively underdeveloped (Mastronardi et al., 2014, Achari and Kowshik, 2018).

Our first results were reported in 1988 representing 2.05% from all USAMVB reports (Anton et al., 1988, 1, 2; Butnaru and Roosz, 1988). Extensive researches started in 1982 when a large part of our university staff was involved in Magnetic Liquids (ML) experiments on plant and animal even on human voluntaries (Goian et al., 1989). Before this date in 1986 Goian and Butnaru in informal conditions presented the utilization of ML for the early sowing of thermophiles plants in soil with low temperatures.

The evolution of LM utilization during 30 years

The scientific results were grouped in 5 year periods (Figures 1 to 6). The data point out the interest to the different topics, new areas of investigation the results of ML utilization in agriculture, animal health and environment.

During 1988-1990 there were presented in 14 papers representing 9.52% from all publications (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: The obtained results at fundamental domain and at plants presented in 1988-1990

Legend: Plants ■; Cell/Histo. ■; DNA/Chromosome ■; Animals ■; Synthesis ■

The germination, plant growth and their fertility, cell activity and chromosome *behaviour* were presented into 4.11%, 3.42% and 1.37% respectively (Borcean et al., 1989; Butnaru and Butnariu, 1989). The cell and subcellular modification in presence of NMP is still of interest (Tominaga et al., 2013, Pieuchot et al., 2015).

In 1989 Goian et al. in a synthesis pointed out the view of ML utilization in biotechnology and agricultural and animal husbandry technologies and in human medicine.

It was the most difficult part of research because we started from zero information and insufficient knowledge.

We had to create out a minimum of information and literature to hold them for our future results comparison. To create trust in the MNP effect it was necessary to broaden our own knowledge as to offer relevant explanations to researchers with very different views in this field. To create our own persuade the experiments were repeated many times in successive cycles till the results were close in minimum 5 of them.

The results were spectacular and were a great support to continue the efforts at other fields.

The 1991-1995 period was fruitful; the 40 scientific papers represent 27.21% from all the papers published over 30 years. At the same time the papers published abroad were considerable (6.80%; Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: The scientific results at different fields presented published in different magazines or proceedings in 1991-1995

Legend: Plants ■; Cell/Histo ■; DNA/Chromosome ■; Animals ■; Biotechnology ■; UV protection ■; Environment ■; Fungi/Bacteria ■; Synthesis ■;

The main results pointed out the MNP capacity to penetrate cell membrane for changing the course of mitoses (Butnaru et al., 1989, Butnaru et al., 1991, Goldstein et al., 2008) and the chromosome behaviour. In lab condition to a high concentration of MNP with 380 Gs/0.0238 g Fe₃O₄ all maize plants were short and the Sk gene was activated in the tassel. In field conditions the plants were shorter than at the control and the expression of Sk gene in the tassels was under 20%. But the conclusion was clear; in some circumstances the MNP have the power to modify the gene activity (Butnaru, 1996).

During 5 years the emulation of investigations was high and new domains of research were identified.

From all the obtained and discussed results or submitted to different reports of grants only 74% were published. In most of the rejected experiments the outcome pointed out an interesting direction of MLs utilization but the scientific argumentation and concern for environment protection was not sufficiently argued. In this period of activity 9 topics were followed from which 4 of them were new. 15% brought the results from biotechnology (Perciuleac et al., 1994) 5% from environment protection and the reaction of animal pathogens (Butnariu, et al., 1995 and Moga-Manzat et al., 1991 respectively) and 2.5% about animal defence from the UV radiation (Sincai et al., 1991).

The results pointed out that the: - Gene pool splitting was the most valuable result (Butnaru and Butnariu, 1995). The Costeni tomato local cultivar of Maramures County segregated in different plant and fruit types (with indeterminate growth/round and with determinate growth/different fruit shapes). From "Tim. 1-1137 FM" genotype with determinate growth was isolated Ileana-2 variety proposed for registration in 2018. It has been established the protection

effect of MNP at UV radiations at plants and animals. The NMLs may be used as a non-invasive material for environment protection.

In the third stage the research work results were quite rich representing 21.77% from all publications with 6.12% abroad (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: The scientific results at different fields presented published in different magazines or proceedings in 1996-2000

Legend: Plants ■; Cell/Histo. ■; Biotechnology ■; Environment ■; Insects ■; Vet. Med/Tumours ■

Other two new fields of research have been initiated: the tumour treatment and insect's behaviour cognition at MNP presence (Sincai et al., 19991, 2, Butnaru, 1997). To understand the mechanism of MNP involvement in the insect's life cycles the *Drosophila melanogaster* was used as model. Apart sensitivity was pointed out of drosophila genotypes. The mutant w+w+ reacted extremely negatively. The wild genotype resisted up to $\theta=3.70 \times 10^{-3} \text{g/cm}^3$.

If the "petite" adults were transferred in standard culture the dimensions were increased but never reached the normal size.

It was also noticed the enhancement of nodulation at alfalfa if the *Rhizobium* inoculums was prepared into solution with a low concentration of MNPs ($\theta=0.037 \times 10^{-3} \text{g/cm}^3$ (Butnaru et al., 1998).

In the 2001-2005 period 24.49% of the papers were published (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: The scientific results at different fields presented published in different journals or proceedings in 2001-2005

Legend: Plants ■; Cell/Histo ■; DNA/Chromosome ■; Biotechnology ■; UV protection ■; Environment ■; Fungi/Bacteria ■; Insects ■; Vet. Med/Tumours ■

At the same time 5.44% of them were presented and published abroad. No new domain was initiated. The accumulated information allowed us to apply MNP in biotechnology and to design new techniques of utilization (Baciu et al., 2004, Butnaru et al., 2004).

At the Saintpaulia plants risen from seeds germinated into NMPs mixtures ($\theta=0.37 \times 10^{-3} \text{g/cm}^3$) the descendants had very different phenotypic expression. Olympia and Ni-Na completely apart varieties were patented (CR. 2264/03 and CR. 2263/03, Butnaru, 2000 and Butnaru and Sarac 2003 respectively). In a proper MLs type and amount the static criteria of quality (Y1) increased by 119% to *Trichogramma* spp. entomophagous used in the ecological agriculture. To $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{LA}/\text{DBS}$ or at $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{LA}/\text{DBS}/\text{DDW}$ and at $\theta=0.231 \times 10^{-3} \text{g/cm}^3$ concentration the viability and prolificacy was higher with 29.33% and 9.49% respectively (Firu, 2004).

In this period of research the important results were deeply examined and practical extension was offered (Fig. 5).

The analysis of chromosomes and DNA was the important subject of our investigation because it offers relevant response to many unclearly solved questions. The results were presented in 3.40% of the total papers. It was concluded that the MNP induced changing in molecular profile of DNA at *Nicotiana tabacum* L. and at triticale at storage proteins profile (Butnaru et al., 2007).

Fig. 5: The scientific results at different fields presented published in different magazines or proceedings in 2006-2009

Legend: Plants ■; Cell/Histo ■; DNA/Chromosome ■; Biotechnology ■; Environment ■; Fungi/Bacteria ■; Insects ■; Synthesis ■

Due to their useful peculiarities for ecological agriculture the Rhizobium bacteria was studied in hydroponic experiments and in field and also molecular analysis were made (Blidar et al., 2006). To have enough information regarding MNP involvement with nitrogen fixing bacteria were studied 2 different Romanian strains of Rhizobium spp.: the R. lupini (LP-83) and R. phaseolus (FL-F8).

In YMA growth medium and in the presence of small concentrations of MNP to $(0.037 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g/cm}^3)$ after 38 days of growth the CFU number (colony-forming unit) was significantly enhanced with an average of 19% and 15.41% at LP-83 and at FL-F8 respectively (Paun, 2007). As usual, at a high concentration of MNP $(3.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g/cm}^3)$ the bacteria growth was repressed. Similar results were obtained by Jurca et al (2003) in the experiments with Bacillus sp.

Rhizobium lupini (LP-83) showed a high adaptability its growth almost equalized the control revealing an average of 99.06%. Based on this property it was proposed to be used for the preservation of the bacteria strains into a mixture of media with MNP. New researches point out the NMP potential to be used in agriculture (Liu and Lal, 2015).

Outside from a financial regulate research the experiments were reduced to minimum and only for practical domains. The interest was to capitalize unused experimental results to formulate new possibility of MNP utilization. The preoccupation was to discover some niches where the ML can be used for practical interest.

It was a normal decrease of results and publications (Fig. 6) but the interest in MNPs utilization is still in our attention.

The biotechnology through in vitro culture pointed out the morphogenesis intensification, root and plantlets rapid growth, a lengthy time preservation and re-juvenilization of senescent caulli. In this field, there are good results, but to establish an appreciated technology more tests are necessary. The negative response to hypogravity was reduced if the plants were watered with diluted solutions of MNP. Those results are useful to plant cultivation for fresh food for cosmonauts.

Fig. 6: The scientific results at different fields presented published in different magazines or proceedings in 2011-2012

Legend: Cell/Histo ■; Fungi/Bacteria ■; Insects ■;

Quantifiable results point out in best mode our work. It was finished 4 PhD theses and 11 student's diploma work. 2 National symposiums, 14 mini-symposiums and round tables were organized. From the 7 patents 2 were patented abroad. 160 scientific papers were published and 22.97% of them were presented and published at International Conferences. "The Frontier: Plant - Magnetic Fluids" published in 1996 by Ed. Mirton Timisoara was the first book in the world dedicated involvement of NMP with plants. It outlined the important results in this domain out of print in a week (Butnaru, 1996). 9 research grants were accepted in which 291 researchers were involved and in this way it was possible to collect a huge amount of data that were used only partially.

We made 12 offers to private companies for the practical utilization of the obtained results (accepted 41.67%).

In our work with *Saintpaulia ionantha* of in vitro culture an unexpected phenomenon was observed. On the injured explants and on vitrified leaves new

plantlets arise from which healthy plants are formed. The same process was observed on potato calli. In MNP presence minituberculs were made in a larger number than usual (30% upper than control). If similar changes can be made in vivo, a new method to increase potato yield could be performed. But in the next decades you won't see FM-plants in the fields.

In vitro conservation of germplasm is promising nanotechnology utilization. The most useful application is for the species and landraces with vegetative proliferation (potatoes, carrots, and Jerusalem artichokes). It is important for the preservation to maintain the biological material in the state of cell viability and its ability to be active when the growth conditions are suitable.

The explants (neoplantlets and calli) of the mentioned species were preserved for 5 years at the room temperature on the same medium MS-0 supplemented with MNPs ($\theta=37 \times 10^{-3} \text{g/cm}^3$). The phenotype of regenerated plants was normal. No chromosomal or molecular analyses were made. For practical reasons it is essential to establish the proper technology for each species and maybe for each genotype.

Even if the MNP utilization has much useful application in agriculture, biotechnology and animal health their utilization implied some risks. The risks are due to unknown aspects. Up to now it is unknown how to detect the MNP traceability in nature and in soil. The capacity of MNP to induce modifications in the DNA, chromosome structure and cellular activity it is a benefit but also a risk.

It is not clear how NPM recognizes cancerous cells and how they interact with normal cells. A few researches are focused on patients' health in general and on their safety on long term.

All risks have to be evaluated and prevented. To protect the environment were performed methods to produce potato tubers free of viruses (Patent: MD. 554/1996) and a technology to enhance the biological parameters on *Trichogramma* spp. (Patent: MD. 1974/2002).

Conclusions

Considering the climatic change the great challenge of the future the application of nanotechnology in agriculture can contribute to its sustainability. Magnetic Nanoparticles' ability consists in acting efficiently upon the genetic stock on the cellular activity and in the life cycle of plants and other organisms.

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CONSUMPTION AND MARKET VALUE FOR THE FISH PRODUCT IN ROMANIA

Marian CONSTANTIN¹, Raluca NECULA¹,
Mihai FRUMUȘELU¹, Iulian DRĂGHICI¹

Abstract. *The present analysis represents an evolutive investigation of the total value and the average purchase price for the main fishes grown in Romania. The evolution of total production in the analysed interval reveals the existence of a two-dimensional discrepancy concerning the quantities of fish, shellfish, cockles, etc. Nation-scale observations identified both declining trends and a moderate increase rate. The increase trend during the analysed years also applies to the total value, as well as to the price rendered as a weighted average. Fluctuations also occur, and they can be regarded as significant increase or decrease, in each particular case. Common carp, seen as the main fishing species in Romania, shows an ascending trend along the years, but also a ceiling price. Its price rises at a higher rate than its quality and value. Concerning the other species, there are variations both in the quantity and the value, together with multiple trends in their pricing: descending for the silver carp, moderate increase bighead carp and golden carp, and very strong trends for the trout.*

Keywords: total amount, fishing species, supply price/evaluation, value quantum.

Introduction

The fish product has always been regarded as one of the main food sources and has therefore been of permanent interest for the social-economic areas of research. But the main question at this stage is to analyse this aspect under the market spectrum. This means knowing this problem particularly concerning the consumption and the market value of this food product. The present study starts from finding out the quantitative level and the value of the results of fish farming and describing it for the main species of fish. The comparative analysis carried out identifies variations both in quantity and value. The study aims at providing adequate answers in threefold form concerning: the imperative of use in human alimentation, which will lead to a higher request; the possibilities of providing fish to the market, both in quantity and quality; the consumer's behaviour as it results from the influence of the main market factors (particularly the price).

¹ University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Bucharest, Romania, email: marianconstantin2014@yahoo.com; raluca_nec@yahoo.com

Materials and methods

The synthetic form of the present study is the result of several investigations made on a research basis and using adequate methods of analysis.

The research basis is centred on the data provided by “Fishstat-AQNS1 for Romania”, the nationwide statistics (*Anuarul Statistic al României, Disponibilitățile de consum ale populației, anul 2016. INS, 2017*) and the direct discussions and debates at the National Agency for Fishing and Aquaculture (ANPA) of Romania.

The data refer to the dynamics of the interval 2009-2016 and were subject to a comparative analysis. Thus, percentage comparison was used to analyse the quantity, value and price within fish farming. The percentage analytical form was used to make a first comparison with the total, but also against the first year of the analysed dynamics, i.e. 2009, for the cumulative set but also within the structure of the main species of fish (common carp, gold fish, bighead carp, dogwood and trout).

The investigation included the interpretative/correlative analysis of the main parametres. It is worth mentioning the *brutto average food consumption per inhabitant* (i.e. the product weight expressed as commercial weight which still needs preparation in order to be used in human alimentation, reckoned as the ratio between the food available for human consumption and the number of inhabitants, i.e. the human population), the *annual netto average food consumption per inhabitant* (i.e. the product quantity expressed in a form more accessible to human consumption), the levels of the brutto and percentage values resulted from comparison.

The use of these criteria in analysing the fish farming results nationwide enabled the identification of variation in quantity and value on the whole, as well as the comparison between the prices occurring at the moments of providing and selling.

The interpretations resulted from the mentioned parametres highlighted the real situation and the causes of the variations on the fish farming market (concerning the offer, price and request).

Results and discussions

The fish product question is seen in form of a balance which can only be analysed by the three-dimensional approach on quantity, total value and average purchase price. All these are rendered using adequate parametres pointing at the real situation of the fish product market in Romania.

I. The evolution of the quantity, value and of the average price reached. These are essential elements in knowing this question, which describe the nationwide structure as shown in Table 1. The results suggest the following interpretations:

Table 1. The (cumulative) results on the quantity and value levels concerning the farming of fish, shellfish, molluscs, etc. in Romania

Year	Total quantity		Value (total brutto)		Average price	
	tons	% compared with 2009	total thousands ron	% compared with 2009	ron/kg (in accordance with the weighted average)	% compared with 2009
2009	13131.0	100	72035.70	100	5.48	100
2010	8981.32	68.39	83480.79	115.88	9.29	169.43
2011	8353.27	63.61	67359.86	93.50	8.06	146.99
2012	10004.0	76.18	80864.37	112.25	8.08	147.34
2013	10146.0	77.26	90545.12	125.69	8.92	162.67
2014	10679.98	81.33	85334.80	118.46	7.99	145.64
2015	11041.748	84.08	97348.98	135.13	8.81	160.71
2016	12554.4	95.60	123829.30	171.89	9.86	179.79

Sursa: Fishstat-AQNS1 for Romania (2016), Form for reporting statistics on agriculture of fish, crustaceans, molluscs, etc., by species environment, and fishing areas.

a) The evolution of the quantities obtained in the nationwide farming of fish, shellfish, molluscs etc., fluctuates on the interval 2009 – 2016, when the following trends can be identified: an annual dropping trend for 2010 – 2011 (the comparison is with the year of reference 2009 and the decrease is of around 1/3 of the level of that year); a successive increasing trend on the interval 2012 – 2016 (with the remark that the recovery in the last year of the interval reaches 95.60% of the 2009 level only).

b) The analysis of the brutto total value for the above-mentioned quantities reveals a continuous growing trend compared to the same year of reference (2009). The rhythm of this growth in value is rendered by a successive yearly increase of +71.98 % in 2016 compared against 2009.

c) A first-order quantitative parameter in the analysis is the average price, rendered as weighted average (RON/kg.) in the succession of the annual fluctuations. The annual levels include variations starting from 5.48 (in 2009) and up to 9.86 RON/kg. (in 2016). The levels of these prices are higher than the level of the year 2009, reaching +79.79 % in the last year of the analysed interval.

All these observations suggest the existence of a two-dimensional gap in both quantity and value. The analysis of such situations needs a deeper investigation centred on the same parameters (of quantity and value) in each of the main species of fish used in fish farming.

II. The quantity and value levels of the main fish farming species of Romania

The analysis has been carried out on the main species nationwide: Carp (Common Carp or European Carp), Golden Carp (or Goldfish), Dogwood (Silver Carp), Big Carp (Novac) and Trout (Brown Trout). The analysis of these fish species during the interval 2009-2016 suggests the following economic impact:

Table 2. The quantity and value levels for the fish species **Common carp / Cyprinus carpio (Crap, Crapul comun sau crapul European)** in Romania

Fish species name (code name in English / scientific name / common name)	Year	Quantity (for the market)			Value (estimated at purveyance / delivery)			Price at purveyance / delivery		
		tons	%		total thousands ron	%		ron/kg	%	
			compared with total	compared with 2009		compared with total	compared with 2009		compared with medie	compared with 2009
Common carp / Cyprinus carpio (Crap, Crapul comun sau crapul European)	2009	4142.0	31.54	100	25473.3	35.36	100	6.15	112.22	100
	2010	2888.1	46.11	69.72	37545.3	44.97	147.39	13.0	139.93	211.38
	2011	2652.051	31.74	64.02	23125.88	34.33	90.78	8.72	108.18	141.78
	2012	3266.0	32.64	78.85	34273.01	42.38	134.54	10.49	129.82	170.56
	2013	3395.0	33.46	81.96	37341.23	41.24	146.58	10.99	123.20	178.69
	2014	3736.65	34.98	90.21	37799.61	44.29	148.38	10.11	126.53	164.39
	2015	4348.86	39.38	104.99	44271.39	45.47	173.79	10.18	115.55	165.52
	2016	4840.8	38.55	116.87	50683.18	40.92	198.96	10.47	106.18	170.24

a) **Common carp** is regarded as the main species of fish farming in Romania. Table 2 displays the structure of the quantity and value levels. Its annual dynamics of quantity and value shows the highest percentage within fish farming (for the market) with annual fluctuations. The highest quantity level is recorded in 2010 (46.11%) and the highest value level in 2015 (45.47%). The comparison with the year 2009 reveals an increase along the succession of years, with the last year of analysis (116.87% and 198.96%, respectively). The supply price shows the same annual increases. Moreover, the analytical comparison of the supply prices reveals a much faster increase rate compared to the quantitative level and the value level. Compared to the year 2009, the supply price has a marked difference in value, which ranges between 141.78% (in 2011) and 211.38% (in 2010).

Table 3. The quantity and value levels for the fish species **Goldfish / Carassius auratus** (**Carasul auriu, Aurul, Peștișorul de aur**) in Romania

Fish species name (code name in English / scientific name / common name)	Year	Quantity (for the market)			Value (estimated at purveyance / delivery)			Price at purveyance / delivery		
		tons	%		total thousands ron	%		ron/kg	%	
			compared with total	compared with 2009		compared with total	compared with 2009		compared with medie	compared with 2009
Goldfish / Carassius auratus (Carasul auriu, Aurul, Peștișorul de aur)	2009	1623.0	12.36	0.09	4057.5	5.63	100	2.5	45.62	100
	2010	933.96	18.07	0.20	3222.16	3.85	79.41	3.45	37.13	138
	2011	1047.68	12.54	0.15	3719.26	5.52	91.66	3.55	44.04	142
	2012
	2013
	2014
	2015
	2016	882.9	7.03	0.05	5359.203	4.32	132.08	6.07	61.56	242.8

Sursa: Fishstat-AQNS1 for Romania (2016), Form for reporting statistics on agriculture of fish, crustaceans, molluscs, etc., by species environment, and fishing areas (Formular pentru raportarea statisticilor privind agricultura peștilor, crustaceelor, moluștelor etc., pe medii de specii și zone de pescuit)

b) Goldfish has the same specific elements of quality and value, as described in Table 3. Concerning the quantity available for the market, one may remark that, during the analysed interval, it varies between 18.07% (in 2010) and 7.03% (in 2016), with a decreasing trend along the years. The same decreasing trend is detected in comparison with 2009. As for the value quantum in relation to the supply quantities, there are levels that differ from the total production of fish farming, ranging between 3.85% and 5.63%. Most of the years analysed show differences at the level of the year 2009, while the year 2016 has a value that is more than +32.08%. Regarding the prices of this species, the percentage levels are much lower than the weighted average, ranging between 53.82% and 91.24%. Compared to the year 2009, the variations have constantly increased, reaching an additional value of +142.8% in 2016.

It is noteworthy that goldfish has a decreasing trend concerning its harvesting, correlated to the same dropping rhythm of the income values and at the same time with a rise in the prices.

Table 4. Nivelul cantitativ și valoric al speciei piscicole **Silver carp / Hypophthalmichthys molitrix (Sângerul, Crapul de argint)** în România

Fish species name (code name in English / scientific name / common name)	Year	Quantity (for the market)			Value (estimated at purveyance / delivery)			Price at purveyance / delivery		
		tons	%		total thousands ron	%		ron/kg	%	
			compared with total	compared with 2009		compared with total	compared with 2009		compared with medie	compared with 2009
		Silver carp / Hypophthalmichthys molitrix (Sângerul, Crapul de argint)	2009	2971.0	22.62	100	14855.0	20.62	100	5.0
2010	2015.51		33.07	67.83	10077.55	12.07	67.83	5.0	53.82	100
2011	1323.23		15.84	44.53	5742.82	8.52	38.65	4.34	53.84	86.8
2012	2087.0		20.86	70.24	10638.82	13.15	71.61	5.09	62.99	101.8
2013	2031.0		20.91	68.36	12188.03	13.46	82.04	6.00	67.26	120
2014	1899.5		17.78	63.93	9075.70	10.63	61.09	4.77	59.69	95.4
2015	1842.72		16.68	62.02	9213.6	9.46	62.02	5.0	56.75	100
2016	2364.0		18.8	79.56	13663.92	11.03	91.98	5.78	58.62	115.6

Sursa: Fishstat-AQNS1 for Romania (2016), Form for reporting statistics on agriculture of fish, crustaceans, molluscs, etc., by species environment, and fishing areas (Formular pentru raportarea statisticilor privind agricultura peștilor, crustaceelor, moluștelor etc., pe medii de specii și zone de pescuit

c) For **dogwood**, the data displayed in Table 4 render the problems related to quantity and value. The analysis of the quantities prepared for the market reveals the occurrence of significant annual variations ranging between 15.84% and 33.07%. Moreover, one may remark the existence of levels which are lower than the level of the year 2009. Concerning the value analysis on the interval 2009 - 2016, both overall and compared to the year 2009, one may remark annual decreases both in relation to the total and to the year 2009. Prices varying between 4.34 (in 2011) and 6.00 lei/kg. (in 2013) suggest annual variations on a dropping trend. The weighted values for each years analysed are lower even than the weighted average for all the years. When these prices are compared to the year 2009, one may remark variations ranging between 86.08% (in 2011) and 115.6% (in 2016).

Thus, dogwood may well have a quantitative representativity, but one may also speak of representativity in value that is given both by low levels and the comparative level of price.

Table 5. The quantity and value levels for the fish species
Bighead carp / Hypophthalmichthys nobilis (Crapul mare, Novac) in Romania

Fish species name (code name in English / scientific name / common name)	Year	Quantity (for the market)			Value (estimated at purveyance / delivery)			Price at purveyance / delivery		
		Tone	%		total thousands ron	%		ron/kg	%	
			compared with total	compared with 2009		compared with total	compared with 2009		compared with medie	compared with 2009
		Bighead carp / Hypophthalmichthys nobilis (Crapul mare, Novac)	2009	2352.0	17.91	100	11760	16.32	100	5.0
2010	1019.98		26.18	43.36	5099.9	6.10	37.37	5.0	53.82	100
2011	1288.64		15.42	54.78	5270.57	7.82	47.91	4.09	50.74	81.8
2012	2110.0		21.09	89.71	9909.87	12.25	75.06	4.69	58.04	93.8
2013	2110.0		20.79	89.71	12662.11	13.98	85.66	6.00	67.26	120
2014	2286.89		21.41	97.23	11566.98	13.55	83.02	5.05	63.20	101
2015	1839.85		16.66	78.22	9548.82	9.80	60.04	5.19	58.91	103.8
2016	2120.5		16.89	90.15	12341.31	9.96	61.02	5.82	59.02	116.4

Sursa: Fishstat-AQNS1 for Romania (2016), Form for reporting statistics on agriculture of fish, crustaceans, molluscs, etc., by species environment, and fishing areas (Formular pentru raportarea statisticilor privind agricultura peștilor, crustaceelor, moluștelor etc., pe medii de specii și zone de pescuit).

d) Regarding **Bighead Carp**, the data displayed in Table 5 give rich information about the quantities, evaluations and supply prices for this species. The quantities range from 2352.0 tons (in 2009) to 1019.98 tons (in 2010). The percentage of these annual levels in the total annual quantities of fish range from 26.18% (in 2010) and 15.42% (in 2011). Compared to the reference year 2009, the levels are lower, with percentage variations between 43.36% (in 2010) and 97.23% (in 2014). The value at the moment of supplying, compared to the total, has levels that range between 6.10% (in 2010) and 16.32% (in 2009). The comparison with the year 2009 reveals levels that are lower each year, the extreme values occurring in 2010 (37.37%) and in 2013 (85.66%) respectively. The supply/delivery prices vary between 4.09 (in 2011) and 6.0 RON/kg. (in 2013), with a percentage variation between 91.24% (in 2006) and 50.74% (in 2011) compared to the average of the overall fish production. The analysis of the prices during the whole interval 2009 – 2016 compared to the year 2009 shows a fall in

these prices to 81.8% in 2011, a level which rises in the next years up to 116.4% in 2016.

All these observations suggest that bighead carp has a dropping trend both in quantity and value, but also a successive annual increase of the level of prices.

Table 6. The quantity and value levels for the fish species
Sea trout / *Salmo trutta* (Păstrăvul, Păstrăvul brun) in Romania

Fish species name (code name in English / scientific name / common name)	Year	Quantity (for the market)			Value (estimated at purveyance / delivery)			Price at purveyance / delivery		
		tons	%		total thousands ron	%		ron/kg	%	
			compared with total	compared with 2009		compared with total	compared with 2009		compared with medie	compared with 2009
		Sea trout / <i>Salmo trutta</i> (Păstrăvul, Păstrăvul brun)	2009	898	6.83	100	8441.2	11.71	100	9.4
2010	900.0		9.99	100.22	13500.0	16.71	159.92	15.0	161.46	159.57
2011	16.91		0.20	1.88	272.31	0.40	3.22	16.1	199.75	171.27
2012
2013
2014
2015	27.21		0.24	3.03	515.35	0.52	6.10	18.9	214.52	201.06
2016	22.0		0.17	2.44	352.0	0.284	4.17	16.0	162.27	170.21

Sursa: Fishstat-AQNS1 for Romania (2016), Form for reporting statistics on agriculture of fish, crustaceans, molluscs, etc., by species environment, and fishing areas (Formular pentru raportarea statisticilor privind agricultura peștilor, crustaceelor, moluștelor etc., pe medii de specii și zone de pescuit)

e) The **trout** species, whose data are displayed in Table 6, is on a decreasing trend both in quantity and value. Thus, concerning its quantity, one may notice a drastic decrease (from 898 tons in 2009 to 22 tons in 2016, which respectively represent 6.83% and 0,17% of the total fish farming). Compared to the year 2009, these percentage levels represent an excessive decrease, ranging between 1.88% and 2.44%. A similar representation has the value levels, rendered by the estimations at the moment of purveyance, which range between 0.284% and 16.71% of the total. Compared to the year 2009, the levels range between 3.22% and 6.105, except for the year 2010. The price of purveyance/delivery reveals, in the case of this species, favourable levels which are over the weighted

average of all the years analysed in this study. Even a comparison to the year 2009 shows values which range between 159.57% and 201.06%.

The analysis conducted on this species leads to the conclusion that the interval 2009 – 2016 is marked by a sharp decrease in quantity and income, but, at the same time, an increase in price.

Conclusions

The synthetic and analytic-structural form of the analysis carried out in this study, on the main fish farming species of Romania during the interval 2009-2016, highlights the main parts of what can be described as a three-dimensional situation of the production, value and price of the fish product in Romania.

1.- The overall nationwide production shows a two-dimensional discrepancy centred on: the evolution of the quantities of fish, shellfish, molluscs, etc., where decreasing trends are present, together with a moderate increase rhythm; concerning the total value of the quantities previously mentioned, there is a successive increase trend along the years analysed; the price, rendered in form of a weighted average, is on an increase trend from year to year (with annual variations that may be regarded as considerable increases/decreases, on a case by case basis).

2.- Common carp, regarded as Romania's most important fish farming species, has the largest percentage of the total, both in quantity and value. Moreover, the quantity/value levels increased compared to the respective levels of the year 2009. It is noteworthy that the price reached its highest level in the last year of the analysis while keeping the same increase trend that was present every year. A comparative survey of the purveyance prices reveals the fact that their increase rate is much faster than the quantitative and value levels.

3.- For the rest of the analysed species, there are variations both in quantity and in value, together with a differentiating trend in prices (a decreasing trend for dogwood, a moderately increasing trend for bighead carp and goldfish, and a very strong increasing trend for trout).

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THE BIOLOGICAL VITICULTURE AND GENOTYPE FUNCTIONALITY

Boris GĂINĂ³, Eugeniu ALEXANDROV⁴

Abstract. *The expected results in modern agriculture can be obtained by applying environmental technologies and taking into account the genotype functionality factor. Knowing the functional properties of the genotype and the use of environmental technologies for growing grapes, in the future it will be possible to create balanced, sustainable and diversified agroecosystems, which will guarantee the protection of natural resources, sustainable development of society and public health. The grape sector needs to create new grape varieties, with stable productive potential, to produce high-quality derived products. As a result of the crossing of the species *V. vinifera* L. ssp. *sativa* D.C. (2n=38) with *Muscadinia rotundifolia* Michx. (2n=40), root-specific genotypes of grapes were obtained, to which ecological cultivation technologies can be applied, for example: Malena, Nistryana and Algumaks as table varieties and Augustine, Alexandrina and Amethyst for fresh consumption and for processing.*

Keywords: biological products, genotype, environment, functionality, ecological viticulture.

Introduction

Society is developing steadily when it consumes high-quality products of natural origin, rationally uses natural resources, and the environmental impact is minimal. Environmental protection is a global problem that should become a national priority, since it directly relates to the living conditions and health of the population, achievement of economic interests, as well as opportunities for sustainable development of society [12, 13]. Sustainable development means that way of development of human society, which is aimed at meeting the needs of the current generation, without affecting the level and quality of life of future generations. Each generation should strive to satisfy its own needs, without leaving various generations of debts for future generations, including environmental ones - depletion of natural resources or pollution of soil, water, air, etc. [13].

Organic viticulture is becoming increasingly popular around the world. This trend is based on a system of technological methods aimed at maintaining the

³ Academician, Academy of Sciences of Moldova, e-mail: b.gaina@mail.ru

⁴ Doctor habilitat in biological sciences, Institute of Genetics, Physiology and Plant Protection, e-mail: e_alexandrov@mail.ru

biodiversity of grapevine, the successful cultivation and consumption of grapes with minimal use of chemical treatments, and therefore with minimal content of their residues in the crop [2, 3, 19].

The development of human society requires special attention to problems related to environmental protection and the rational use of natural resources. There is no doubt that it is necessary to know the possibilities of the genetic potential of genotypes depending on climatic conditions, which have a significant impact on programming the quantity and quality of products [13].

Agriculture, depending on pedo-climatic and socio-economic conditions, should provide the population with high-quality food-derived natural products, supply of raw materials for industry, rational use of natural resources and conservation of biodiversity. One of the main tasks of agriculture is the identification of new genotypes that can easily adapt and develop in the context of climate change without harming the environment. To achieve this goal, you need to have genotypes with increased functionality.

Derived grape and wine products make a significant contribution to the development of the country's economy, and therefore it is necessary to pay special attention to the creation of vineyards with the introduction of environmental cultivation technologies. It is necessary to create genotypes with increased functionality and the choice of technology for growing grapes, which would allow to obtain high-quality and high productivity, with a minimum number of protection products, and maybe without them, thereby preserving the environment and biological diversity, as well as the presence of a minimum of these substances in berries and grape and wine-derived products [6, 7, 9, 14, 15].

To obtain the highest quality grape and wine derivatives, three main factors must be taken into account: genotype (variety), location of the vineyard (pedo-climatic conditions) and technology (cultivation and processing). Despite the fact that *Vitis vinifera* L. ssp. *sativa* D.C. has a high genetic potential, yet intraspecific genotypes cannot cross the genetic barrier of high sensitivity to changes in climatic conditions within the growing area, therefore it is necessary to create interspecific genotypes with high-quality products and resistant to environmental factors [6, 7, 9, 10 - 12, 14].

A research on this issue was carried out by the Research Institute of Organic Agriculture, in Switzerland, which published data on the total area of organic vineyards in the world. In 2015, this area was more than 400 thousand hectares. It has been found out that the transition of vineyards from traditional to organic technologies takes 3 years, after which the grape harvest is considered to comply with the established requirements. As for the growth rate of the area of vineyards cultivated according to the organic technologies, it was established that from 2005 to 2015, it trebled. The world leaders, in terms of area of organic vineyards and production of organic grapes, are Spain – with 85 thousand

hectares, France – 75 thousand hectares, Italy – 65 thousand hectares, Mexico – 35 thousand hectares and China – 20 thousand hectares. Currently, the shares of areas of organic vineyards in European countries are as follows: Austria – 10.7 %, Italy – 10.3 %, Spain – 8.9 %, France – 8.7 %, Germany – 7.5 %, Portugal – 1.5 % [15]. More than 270 thousand hectares of organic vineyards are cultivated on the European continent, which makes up 67.5 % of the total area of organic vineyards in the world. This new trend in grape cultivation is developing rapidly in China, Turkey, Italy, Germany, Argentina, Chile, Australia and South Africa.

Materials and methods

The subject of the research was the collection of grapevine plants of the Institute of Genetics, Physiology and Plant Protection, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova. The collection includes 140 genotypes of interspecific and intraspecific, grafted and own-rooted genotypes of grapevine. The method of distant hybridization was used to create interspecific own-rooted genotypes of grapevine [4-7]. Studies were conducted in accordance with the methods of describing grapevine varieties [1, 8, 9], Methodical Recommendations for Grapevine Breeding, Study of grapes to determine how to use them. Uvology [11, 22]. The physicochemical assessment of derivative products of interspecific genotypes of grapes was performed in accordance with the methods for analysing derivative products [12, 10, 16]. To determine the resistance of the studied genotypes to phylloxera, pathogenic microorganisms etc., the methods mentioned in Normal and Pathological Anatomy of Grapevine Roots and Complex Protection of Grapevine [14-17, 21, 22] were used.

Results and discussions

Based on the functionality of grape taxa, it is possible to create genotypes that will provide an opportunity to increase the efficiency of interspecific hybridization of grapes in the process of improving valuable qualities. But, in order to achieve the set goal and obtain results, it is necessary to evaluate the genotypes included in the selection process from the point of view of functionality in relation to pedagogical conditions. To determine the functionality of genotypes, a comparative analysis of ampelographic, agrobiological, technological and physiological properties in relation to climate change is necessary. Taxa with enhanced functionality must be included in the process of creating interspecific genotypes based on pedo-climatic conditions.

In the process of selection of grapes, it is necessary to take into account the functional properties of the genotype: growing technology; fertility; productivity (in relation to the vegetative period and pedo-climatic zone); ratio of growth and fertility; histo-anatomical and biochemical properties; resistance to diseases and pests; resistance to low temperatures; the chemical composition of

berry juice and derivatives (wine, distillate, etc.); bunch ripening (early - later); the appearance of a bunch; pulp properties; aroma and taste; resistance to cracking berries; the ability to store and transport grapes; use (fresh use); processing (wine, distillate, juice, etc.); recycling [1, 9, 10, 20].

Knowing the functional properties of the genotype and the use of environmental technologies for growing grapes, in the future it will be possible to ensure the creation of balanced, sustainable and diverse agroecosystems, which will guarantee the protection of natural resources, sustainable development of society and public health.

Ecotechnologies contribute to the creation of a variety of sustainable balanced agroecosystems, the rational use of natural resources, the reduction of the use of polluting technologies, the restriction of the use of chemical-synthetic substances and the reduction of potentially destructive agricultural work.

In the European market, there is a great demand for organic grapes, and it equally applies to grapes intended for consumption while fresh (table varieties) and those for the production of wine and distilled drinks. The organic cultivation of grapevine leads, on the one hand, to a reduction in the contamination of grapes with residues of the substances used to protect them from diseases and pests, and on the other hand, to a lower degree of environmental pollution (soil, water and air) [11, 12, 15].

The European Union supports organic viticulture, by subsidizing this type of activity of winegrowers (at the transition stages from traditional to organic cultivation of grapevine), covering the losses of economic agents whose vineyards have suffered from hail, epiphytotic diseases and prolonged rains that have led to crop loss. However, taking into account the fact that the demand for organic grapes (table and wine grapes) is constantly raising, not only in Europe, but also in North America and East Asia, at present, their price is 40-60 % or even 100 % higher. This, of course, attracts winegrowers, and today about 10 % of vineyards in the countries of the European Union are certified as “organic”. In France, in Alsace, some programs have been created to inform people about the peculiarities of the organic cultivation of grapevine, and their students are representatives of the grape-growing and winemaking industry of most EU countries, as well as Canada, the USA, Israel, Australia, New Zealand, China etc.

Currently, the technology of cultivation of organic grapevine must be consistent with certain standards: for example, the use of copper is limited to 3 kg per hectare per year, and the maximum sulphur application – 6 kg per hectare per year. There are countries where these standards differ in the direction of a slight decrease, but in all cases, the extract (infusion) of nettle, bark and leaves of oak, leaves of walnut, calendula etc. are widely used along with fungicides based on copper and sulphur.

However, the cultivation of grapes according to the organic technologies in the Republic of Moldova faces certain difficulties, which are the main reason behind the slow introduction of this new trend of the grape-growing and winemaking. One of them is the absence of biopreparations, produced on an industrial basis, to inhibit the growth of micromycetes (*Botrytis cinerea* etc.) and pests (leafroller moths etc.). For example, in France, a biopreparation made from *Trichoderma viride* is produced under the brand name Trichodermin B14; it has been proven to suppress the growth of mould fungi on berries and leaves in rainy weather by more than 60 % [13]. However, it has been found that this biofungicide loses a part of its action during the months with dry weather (August-September) which reduces the effectiveness of the treatment and increases the risk of micromycete infection at the beginning of the rainy period (September-October) [18]. Moreover, it has been found that the action of Trichodermin B14 is inhibited by residues of copper ions on leaves and berries, which remain after previous treatments of vineyards. In this case, the scientists from the French National Institute for Agricultural Research [3] have begun to grow the biomass of the antagonist *Trichoderma viride*, against grey mould, enriched with copper ions. Under these conditions, the biofungicide was resistant to the inhibiting effect of copper residues on leaves and berries and provided more than 75 % growth inhibition in mould fungi.

Another problem in organic viticulture is the isolation of areas with grapevine in the stages of conversion (within 3 years) from those cultivated nearby, by traditional technology. As a rule, the easiest way of solving this problem is to choose an entire vineyard (plantation), surrounded by other agricultural crops (fodder grasses, sometimes cereals etc.), or shelterbelts, often encountered in our country. The generally accepted rules for organic cultivation of grapes also stipulate the absence of any source of chemical or biological pollution (wastewater treatment plants, chemical plants, landfills etc.). In our opinion, the prices for the certification of plantations, which have been established by international organizations, licensed in this regard, are too high and unjustified, especially in cases of small plantations of grapes and other berries, fruits etc.

Other advantages of organic methods are a significant reduction in environmental pollution, lower costs for the purchase and use of expensive chemicals, as well as higher sale prices for wine and table grapes. In the EU markets, the price of certified organic grapes is 40-60 % or even 100 % higher as compared with the price of grapes cultivated by traditional methods.

Among the main problems faced by this new technology of cultivation of grapevine, there are the difficulties of using classical varieties of the genus *Vitis vinifera* L., because of the high susceptibility to the attack of micromycetes and pests, and the low frost tolerance. These are very important factors under the harsh conditions of the continental climate in our country, with high humidity and

heavy rains in spring, which create favourable conditions for the development of dangerous diseases and pests, and which complicate the timely and effective use of chemical remedies in the framework of the organic technology. On the other hand, in the second half of summer and early autumn, the weather contributes to the development of other diseases, among which, powdery mildew (caused by *Oidium*) and grey mould of grapes are the most dangerous. The way out of this difficult situation may be the wide use of new grapevine varieties with higher resistance to biotic and abiotic environmental conditions [4]. The last fifty years of breeding grapevine have resulted in the creation of some promising varieties of wine grapes to be cultivated by organic methods: Viorica, Legend, Riton, Luminita, (Moldova), Bianca, Chardonel, Aletta, (Hungary), Vidal Blanc, Triumph of Alsace, Shamborsin (France), Fleurtaï, Soreli, Savignon Cretos, Julius, Sagiovese etros, Merlot Chorus, Cabernet, Jerez, Julio, Caberigne Cretos, Julius, Sagiovese etret (Italy), Cabernet Jura, Pinotin, Cabernet blanc (Switzerland), Aromatny, Muscat Odessa, Zagreus, Rubin Tairovsky, Aghat Tairovsky, Golubok, Illichivsky early, Sparkling, Ovidiopol, Odessa Black, Rodnichek etc. (Ukraine). Grapevine varieties with high resistance to diseases and pests have been obtained and recommended for breeding and cultivation in Crimea – by the Institute of Viticulture and Winemaking “Magarach”, in Russia – by the All-Russian Research Institute of Viticulture and Winemaking “Ya.I. Potapenko”, in Bulgaria – by the National Institute of Viticulture and Oenology in Pleven, in Romania – by the Research and Development Institute for Viticulture and Winemaking “Valea Călugărească”. However, the above-listed varieties are susceptible to phylloxera, which makes it necessary to create vineyards from planting material grafted on phylloxera-resistant rootstocks. The viticulture sector needs new grape varieties, with stable productive potential, for the production of high-quality derivative products. The European grapevine varieties of *Vitis vinifera* L. ssp. *sativa* D.C., registered in the Republic of Moldova, as well as in other wine-producing countries, are susceptible to phylloxera (*Phylloxera vastatrix* Planch.) and that is why vineyards should be created from planting material grafted on phylloxera-resistant rootstocks. Besides, because grapevine is sensitive to low temperatures in winter, additional measures are necessary to protect plants during the period of vegetative rest [1, 7, 22].

To obtain competitive products, it is necessary to use mandatory chemical treatments to prevent or destroy pests, micromycetes and other pathogenic agents. However, these treatments affect the cost of production and pollute the environment. The creation of own-rooted grapevine plantations is a good prospect, but for this, it is necessary to enrich the grape assortment with new genotypes, resistant to diseases and pests. As a result of research, a methodology was developed for the creation of own-rooted interspecific genotypes of grapevine *Vitis vinifera* L. ssp. *sativa* D.C. x *Muscadinia rotundifolia* Michx., resistant to

biotic and abiotic factors. Donors of valuable agrotechnological traits were included in the breeding process, as a result of which high-quality, stable and productive grapevine genotypes were created [2, 7].

Mastering the biological potential of interspecific genotypes will allow obtaining high-quality products from grapes, reducing costs and the use of chemicals in the process of controlling micromycetes and pests. The created genotypes have significant agrobiological and technological potential, which allows developing further research in the field of genetics and breeding of grapevine, using the method of distant hybridization. Thus, after of crossing *V. vinifera* x *M. rotundifolia*, interspecific genotypes of grapevine have been created in BC₃, with acquired agrobiological and technological properties, which allow expanding the area where grapevine can be cultivated in the northern regions and reducing the number of chemical treatments that will contribute to obtaining ecological products and protecting the environment. In the process of identifying the genetic functionality of the related taxa, *V. vinifera* and *M. rotundifolia*, characterized by low combining ability, it was found that this obstacle could be overcome by backcrossing. A wide range of recombinants, which allows improving the efficiency of distant hybridization in the process of selection of valuable characteristics, has been obtained as a result of this process [4, 5, 7].

The differences in the classification of interspecific genotypes of grapevine based on DNA profiles (SSR markers) and ampelographic criteria prove the importance of *genotype x environment* specific interactions in the development of biological and technological features of the hybrid. The multilateral research on biological and agrotechnological features, the participation in hybridization of the genotypes of different ecological and geographical origin of *V. vinifera* and *M. rotundifolia* and the elimination of aneuploid forms during subsequent crosses leads to the stabilization of the interspecific genome ($2n = 38$) with valuable agrobiological features and stability. The interspecific genotypes *V. vinifera* x *M. rotundifolia* can be propagated by cuttings from own-rooted, competitive planting material, to obtain early-ripening grapes [7].

When creating new grapevine varieties, by interspecific and intraspecific hybridization, it is very important to take into account the concentration, in the berries, of such chemicals as resveratrol, which ensures the resistance of the plant to adverse environmental factors. A comparative analysis of the concentration of resveratrol in the juice of wild grapes and its concentration in the berries, obtained after hybridization, has shown that, in the juice of wild grapes, the concentration of resveratrol is approximately two times higher than in subsequent generations, obtained as a result of hybridization. That is, as more generations are created, moving away from the wild representatives of the species, the concentration of resveratrol in the juice of the grapes keeps decreasing. The created interspecific

genotypes of grapevine have been studied in detail according to agrobiological and technological criteria [2, 7].

The evaluation of the quality of grapes and derived products, over the years, has made it possible to select and cultivate promising own-rooted genotypes of grapevine. The interspecific genotypes of *V. vinifera* x *M. rotundifolia* are easily propagated by cuttings and can be cultivated on their own roots, thereby offering the opportunity to skip some practical steps, as well as reduce financial costs in the process of producing planting material and growing grapevine. According to the uvological and oenological criteria, the grapes of the new genotypes are not inferior to the classical varieties of *V. vinifera* in their biochemical composition and organoleptic qualities. Besides, they can be grown in the northern areas, where most plants of *Vitis vinifera* L. ssp. *sativa* D.C. do not withstand low temperatures in winter. Studying the physicochemical properties of blue-violet grapes of the interspecific genotypes (*Vitis vinifera* L. x *Muscadinia rotundifolia* Michx.), it has been found that phenols, resveratrol and pectins are present in them in larger quantities than in green-yellow grapes, also exceeding the amount of these substances in the berries of the varieties of *V. vinifera* L. The quantity of resveratrol in the juice of berries of the interspecific genotypes of grapevine is 6.68 mg/l in berries with a green-yellow hue (BC₃-510 etc.), 9.3 mg/l in berries with a pink hue (BC₃-520 etc.) and 14 mg/l in berries with a blue-violet hue (BC₂-3-1, BC₃-660 etc.). From the populations of interspecific genotypes BC₃ (*V. vinifera* x *M. rotundifolia*), several promising own-rooted varieties have been selected, among them, there are table grapes, such as Malena, Nistreana and Algumax, and wine grapes: Augustina, Alexandrina and Ametist [3, 5, 7].

Using the biological potential of interspecific genotypes will make it possible to obtain high-quality derivative products under conditions of organic farming, which implies a reduction in the use of synthetic and natural chemicals in the fight against diseases and pests.

Conclusions

1. From the populations of interspecific genotypes BC₃ (*V. vinifera* x *M. rotundifolia*), several promising own-rooted varieties of table grapes have been selected, such as Malena, Nistreana and Algumax, and other selected varieties, such as Augustina, Alexandrina and Ametist, can be used as table grapes too, but also as wine grapes.

2. Growing interspecific genotypes of grapevine will decrease the negative impact on the environment by reducing the number of chemical treatments.

3. Due to the high resistance of distant hybrids to pests and diseases, the costs associated with the creation of planting material are reduced. Besides, as mentioned above, the number of chemical treatments during the cultivation process is reduced, thus minimizing environmental pollution.

4. In addition, the area of cultivation of grapevine can be expanded to the north, where the climatic conditions are unfavourable for the varieties of *V. vinifera*, which cannot tolerate the low winter temperatures, while the studied interspecific genotypes are more winter-hardy.

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ORGANIC FARMING IN ROMANIA. CURRENT LEVEL AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS IN ROMANIA AND EU

Marian CONSTANTIN⁵, Raluca NECULA⁶, Iulian DRĂGHICI⁴

Abstract. *In this work at the level of the 2010-2018 period, the current levels and the perspective of organic crops in Romania and the EU were sought to be played. Overall, there is a tendency to increase areas cultivated especially for cereal, industrial, grassland and meadow crops. In the structure of the organic production flow → the market there is the same tendency to increase the number of operators with the expansion of organically grown areas.*

EU-wide analysis of organic farming concerned: the pace of growth of areas for organic crops and actual cultivated surfaces; the differentiated level of these surfaces in the structure of the countries and the market of organic agri-food products within the EU market.

Keywords: area actually cultivated ecologically, ecological crop, ecological operator, SAU (used agricultural surface), growth rate, TRACES (trade and expertise control system).

Introduction

The organic farming is a problem discussed with a lot of urgency in the current stage given the multiple implications that are rebraking on the human food system. The initial elements imply knowledge of the ecological production possibilities, forms and current level of cultivation at territorial level. For Romania, it can be said that these potentialities exist. The problems that are being made, for our country, are quantitative, referring to the ways of expanding and structuring the surfaces of different cultures, and qualitative in terms of production[1].

The work aims: an analysis of the size and structure of the surfaces for the main cultures and groups of organic crops for the period 2010-2018; a comparison of ecological surfaces and retail sales of these products; Analysis of the importation of organic products within the EU; analysis and control system and traceability information by the number of environmentally certified operators falling within the categories of producers, processors, distributors and exporters/importers [2, 6].

The whole analysis of these links gives a knowledge of organic agriculture in our country, and allows for a comparative analysis with other EU countries.

⁵ Academy of Romanian Scientists, email: marianconstantin2014@yahoo.com

⁶ University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Bucharest, email: raluca_nec@yahoo.com; if07iul@gmail.com

Materials and methods

The methodology in the study carried out was based on the existing values at national level for the period 2010-2018 : organically cultivated surfaces in total and in the structure of the main groups of crops and the number of ecological certified operators.

The comparative analysis consisted in: comparisons compared to 2010 (considered basic); The comparison in the annual structure of the crop group surfaces compared to the total organic cultivated areas; Percentage analysis that renders the annual variation of certified organic operators (based on the year 2010). The growth rate has been calculated, indicating in relative sizes how much the phenomenon researched each year has increased/decreased during the period analysed [2, 6].

In graphic form, the control system for products obtained in the EU is rendered, but also the percentage level of traceability information for these products.

Results and discussions

Knowledge of organic agriculture at national level was based on the analysis of results in the appearance of actual achievements, at the level of Romania and EU countries [2, 6].

1. **The area of organic crops and ecological operators** was analysed through the levels rendered in the dynamics of the period 2010-2018 from which the following may be said (table 1):

Table 1. Areas for organic crops and number of operators in Romania

Specify	Um	2010	2012	2014	2015	2017	2018	Annual Growth Rhythm (%)
Ecological destination Surfaces	Thousand ha	182.7	288.3	289.3	245.9th	258.5	326.3	7.52
	%	100.0	157.8	158.3	134.6	141.5	178.6	X
Eco-certified Operators	Total number	3155	15544	14470	12231	8434	9008	14.01
	%	100.0	492.7	458.6	387.7	267.3	285.5	X
	Ha on operator	57.9th	18.5	20.0	20.1	30.6	36.2	-5.70

Source:[5]Dynamics of operators and surfaces in organic agriculture, MADR, <https://www.madr.ro/agricultura-ecologica/operatori-exclusi-din-sistemul-de-agricultura-ecologica-de-catre-oic.html>; INS, Eurostat

- The area intended for organic crops in the analyzed dynamics has an ascending variation. This area was in the year 2010 of 182.7 thousand ha and ascended in 2018 to 326.3 thousand ha, which represents towards the base year 2010, a level of growth of + 78.1%;

- Annual growth rate on this period is by 7.52%;
- The number of ecological operators (which means the total number of manufacturers, processors, distributors and exporters/importers), is structured according to EU requirements (*fig. 1*). In the analysis carried out at national level, the annual increases of organic operators reached a maximum of 15544 in the year 2012, followed by a decrease that reaches 9008 in the year 2018. The same variations also result from the comparison with the base year 2010. The annual growth rate for the dynamics of the number of operators is 14.01%.
- The area that returns to an operator is 57.9 ha in the year 2010 and 36.2 ha in the year 2018, with an annual decrease of 5.7%.

2. The structure of areas intended for organic crops in Romania (table 2a and Table 2b), represents the aspect indicating the degree of attraction in the crops repatisation for the SAME period 2010-2018. The values shown in table 2A and 2b are the areas of these cultures, but also comparative levels in relation to their total areas of these cultures, as compared to the base year 2010.

Fig. 1. The management system (control) structure for organic products obtained in the EU [4]

From the analysis, by crop groups, the following interpretations result:

Table 2a. The size and dynamics of the main indicators of organic crops, for the period 2010-2018

Specify	MU	2010	2012	2014	2016	2018	Annual Growth Rhythm (%)
Ecological cultivated surfaces	Ha	182,706	288,261	289,252	226,309	326,260	7.52
Total Grains	Ha	72,298	105,149	102,531	75,198	114,427	5.91
	% total vs. Eco. surface	39.57	36.47	35.44	33.22	35.07	X
	% versus 2010	100	145.43	141.81	104.01	158.27	X
Dried vegetables and protein crops for the production of grains	Ha	5,560	2,764	2,314	2,204	8,751	5.83
	% total vs. Eco. surface	3.04	0.95	0.79	0.9	2.68	X
	% versus 2010	100	49.71	41.61	39.64	157.39	X
Tuberculiferous Plants and total roots	Ha	504	1125	627	707	506	0.05
	% total vs. Eco. surface	0.27	0.39	0.21	0.31	0.15	X
	% versus 2010	100	223.21	124.4	140.27	100.39	X
Industrial crops	Ha	47,815	44,789	54,145	53,397	80,193	6.68
	% total vs. Eco. surface	26.17	15.53	18.71	23.59	24.57	X
	% versus 2010	100	93.67	113.23	111.67	167.71	X
Plants harvested Green	Ha	10,325	11,083	13,494	14,281	28,254	13.41
	% total vs. Eco. surface	5.65	3.84	4.66	6.31	8.65	X
	% versus 2010	100	107.34	130.69	138.31	273.64	X
Other crops on arable land	Ha	580	28	30	258	113	-18.49
	% total vs. Eco. surface	0.31	0.01	0.01	0.11	0.03	X
	% versus 2010	100	4.82	5.17	44.48	19.48	X

Source: [5] Dynamics of operators and surfaces in organic agriculture, MADR, <https://www.madr.ro/agricultura-ecologica/operatori-exclusi-din-sistemul-de-agricultura-ecologica-de-catre-oic.html>

-In the group of cereal crops, industrial crops (with an intensive degree of crop), it can be noted in the evolution of the period analysed the existence of annual

increases. Compared to the year 2010 the most significant increases in the year 2018 are recorded in cereals (with + 58.27%), to which vegetables can be added (+ 57.39%, growth rate of 5.83%) and industrial crops (+ 67.71%, growth rate of 6.68%). For the same crops by comparison with the total area of organic crops in the last year, the grain crops (by 35.07%) and industrial crops (by 24.57%) can be highlighted on the one hand, and on the other hand beans crops (with 2.68%) and tuberculiferous plants (with 0.15%);

-for horticultural crops in the ecological system the share of occupied surfaces is much lower (it registers levels in vegetables limits of 0.30% and 0.66%, and at orchards between 1.69% and 5.69%). In the evolution of the analysed period there are increases compared to year 2010 but at which annual levels vary greatly the last year 2018 compared to the base year 2010, increases of about six times are recorded;

Table 2B. (continuation) Size and dynamics of the main indicators of organic crops, for the period 2010-2018

Specify	Um	2010	2012	201	2016	2018	Annual Growth Rhythm
Fresh vegetables (including melons) and strawberries	Ha	734	896	1,928	1,175	983	3.72
	% total vs. Eco. surface	0.4	0.31	0.66	0.51	0.3	X
	% versus 2010	100	122.07	262.67	160.08	133.92	X
Vineyards, orchards, fruit shrubs, nuts, etc.	Ha	3,093	7,781	9,439	12,020	18,569	25.11
	% total vs. Eco. surface	1.69	2.69	3.26	5.31	5.69	X
	% versus 2010	100	251.56	305.17	388.61	600.35	X
Permanent crops grassland and meadow	Ha	31,579	105,836	95,685	57,612	66,890	9.84
	% total vs. Eco. surface	17.28	36.71	33.08	25.45	20.5	X
	% versus 2010	100	335.14	303	182.43	211.81	X
Fallow land	Ha	10,217	8,811	9,059	9,457	7,573	-3.67
	% total vs. Eco. surface	5.59	3.05	3.13	4.17	2.32	X
	% versus 2010	100	86.23	88.66	92.56	74.12	X

Source: [5]Dynamics of operators and surfaces in organic agriculture, madr, <https://www.madr.ro/agricultura-ecologica/operatori-exclusi-din-sistemul-de-agricultura-ecologica-de-catre-oic.html>

-the category of use of grassland and meadows in the ecological system occupies areas to which significant variations are growing (compared with total ecological crops between 17.2% and 36.7%, and compared to the base year of comparison 2010 variations are between 160.5% and 335.1%). The annual growth rate is 9.84%;

-Fallow land, waiting, i.e. during the preparing period, appear in the records, occupying national surfaces between 10,217 ha and 7,573 ha. In the dynamics of the years, there is a decrease that compared to the total cultivated land at which the variation presents a void succesivity, which is between 5.59% (year 2010) and 2.32% (year 2018), and the decrease in the year 2010 is between 95.51% (year 2011) and 74.12% (year 2018).The annual growth rate is 3.67%;

The analysed structural ensemble reveals an increase in areas for organic crops at national level, but in different rhythms. To mention the group of cereal crops, industrial, grassland and meadow, which have the highest weights, with the groups of horticultural plants, tuberculials and those harvested green with a much lower level. But with these growths of organic crops we also find a decrease in the land highlighted in the ecological system but still uncultivated.

3. *The analysis of the structural level of areas actually cultivated organically and the commercial sales amount for organic products in EU countries, for the period 2000-2017*(table 3), has highlighted the following aspect:

- for EU, the areas actually cultivated are growing. Compared with SAU (the agricultural area used) an annual amplification is found, of which levels record an annual increase between 5.1% (in 2010) and 7.03% (in 2017), at which the rate of growth is by 4.69%;

- in the countries analysed, differentiated situations can be presented which structurally can be rendered as follows: *a)* countries with significant areas of areas actually cultivated organically (Austria and Sweden) whose shares are compared with SAU vary between 18.40 – 23.27% and 14.3-19.16% respectively, growth rhythms recording percentage levels of 2.62% and 4.27%; *b)* countries with moderate levels of ecological cultivated areas (France and Germany) annual weights ranging from 2.9-5.99% and respective 5.90-6.82%, at which growth rhythms are between 10.92% and 2.09%; *c)* The Exsocialite countries (Romania, Hungary, Bulgaria and Poland), which record the lowest levels, under the weighted comparative aspect, are in the year 2010 between 0.5% and 3.3%, and in the year 2017 between 1.93% and 3.73%, growth rhythms are located between 0.47% and 6.50%.

Table 3. The share of the area actually cultivated organically vs. SAU and the pace of growth in the main EU countries (%)

Country	2010	2012	2014	2015	2016	2017	Annual growth Rhythm (%)
Eu	5.1	5.66	5.78	6.2	6.68	7.03	4.69
Romania	1.3	2.1	2.09	1.77	1.67	1.93	5.81
France	2.9	3.55	3.87	4.54	5.29	5.99	10.92
Germany	5.9	5.76	6.18	6.34	6.82	6.82	2.09
Hungary	2.4	2.45	2.34	2.43	3.48	3.73	6.50
Bulgaria	0.5	0.76	0.96	2.37	3.2	2.72	27.38
Sweden	14.3	15.76	16.53	17.14	18.13	19.16	4.27
Poland	3.3	4.51	4.56	4.03	3.72	3.41	0.47
Austria	19.5	18.62	19.35	20.3	21.25	23.37	2.62

Source:[3, 4, 6, 7]INS, Eurostat

The annual dynamic of the period 2000-2017 is given in the cumulative figure at the European level in *fig. 2*.

It can be noted that the EU's ecological sector has developed at an accelerated pace with regard to the agricultural area involved. Thus, the total area of agricultural land used for organic farming in the EU increased from 9.1 million hectares in 2010 to 12 million hectares in 2016, which represents an increase of 33%. In 2016, the proportion of agricultural land in the EU for organic production compared to total SAU was 6.7%. [4, 6].

Fig. 2.-The aggregate growth of the area used for organic farming and retail sales in Europe (period 2000-2017) [7]

Overall, it can be noted, for the period mentioned, an increase in areas cultivated in the year 2017, which has a growth rate of more than two times compared to the level of 2000.

The analysis by the same annual developments on retail sales for organic products highlights the existence of much more accentuated increases, so that in the year 2017 compared to 2000 these increases are more than four times higher. It can also be found that this value of retail sales of organic products has risen from 18.1 billion EUR in the year 2010 to 30.7 billion EUR in 2016, which represents an increase of 69% (Fig. 2) [7]. The main 20 exporting countries, from a total of 114 countries, are played in Fig. 3 at the level of year 2018.

Norway and Switzerland are not included in this graph, since the Commission's trade control and expertise System (TRACES) did not include/contains any information on exports from these countries.

Fig. 3. Ranking of the main 20 countries from which organic products were imported into the EU in 2018 (depending on weight) [4]

It should be noted that from the total of imported organic products, approximately 87% are certified by equivalent control bodies (i.e. India, Argentina, Tunisia, Israel, Chile). (4)

Conclusions

From the whole paper on organic farming presented at national level alongside the achievements and comparisons played for EU countries, the following can be concluded:

1. In Romania both the area for organic crops and the areas actually cultivated for the period analysed record annual increases. Linked to these surface

increases and the number of operators is increasing, a decrease in the areas returning to an operator is also found.

2. From the analysis of the structure of surfaces intended for organic crops in Romania, an annual rhythm that is growing (compared with 2010) can be deduced and a variation of their annual level. The level of annual recorded rhythms (compared to the total of the ecological cultivated surface), relies a significant differentiation in the sense of the prevalence of cereal, industrial, grassland and meadow crops, alongside much lower levels existing in other cultures.

3. The control in the structure of the management system appropriate to the activities for the operators of the ecological system, the nomination by operations carried out (producers, stores, processes, transports, exports or imports of organic products) shall be specified. At national level, the increase in the number of operators is highlighted.

4. The comparative analysis carried out at the level of EU countries can highlight the following aspects: increasing the surfaces actually cultivated organically; growth rhythms record the highest levels of ecological surfaces for Bulgaria and France; the exsocialist countries are increasing significantly lower ecological surfaces compared to the EU average.

5. In relation to the market for organic products: The retail growth of organic products is much more pronounced than the increase in ecological production areas; the market for organic products for the EU highlights a massive import of these products from about 120 countries.

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EXPLOITATION OF BAUXITE FROM PADUREA CRAIULUI MOUNTAINS AND THE IMPACT ON ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

Radu BREJEA⁷, Cristian DOMUTA⁸, Eugen JUDE⁹, Andrei NISTOR¹⁰

Abstract. *The paper presents the impact of the exploitation of bauxite in the Pădurea Craiului Mountains on the environmental factors. The extraction of bauxite was carried out by surface quarries and underground galleries. Exploitation of this field irrespective of the established method produces a significant impact on environmental factors. For this reason it is compulsory to establish some works, solutions that will lead to the restoration and ecological reconstruction of these mining perimeters, whether they are quarries, tailings dumps or tailings ponds. The present paper presents bauxite quarries in Zece Hotare, Bihor County, the impact on the environment as well as a series of technical measures to reproduce the economic cycle of degraded and polluted land.*

Keywords: bauxite, quarry, galleries, pollution, environment.

1. Introduction

Bauxite is an ore or a mixture of mineral substances, consisting mainly of aluminium hydrates, iron oxide, alumina silicate and titanium oxide. The bauxites appear in amorphous compact or earth mass, and the most sought-after bauxites are those with low silica content (SiO₂).

The country with the largest production of bauxite in the world is Australia. It is followed by Guinea and Brazil. A remarkable growth of bauxite production was recorded in China, India and Jamaica.

During 1990-2006, Romania appears as a bauxite producer. Since there were bauxite deposits in Transylvania there were also various attempts to set up an aluminium industry to capitalize on this deposit. The interest for the bauxite ore in the Pădurea Craiului Mountains manifested after 1900. Its exploitation also took place before and during the First World War, but preferentially, i.e.

⁷ University lecturer, PhD, engineer BREJEA Radu - Corresponding Member of the Academy of Romanian Scientists, University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection

⁸ University lecturer, PhD, engineer DOMUTA Cristian - University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection

⁹ Senior lecturer, PhD, engineer – JUDE Eugen - University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection

¹⁰ PhD Student, engineer NISTOR Andrei - University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection

exploitation made of ore bodies located at the surface, namely at Tomnatic, Zece Hotare, Valea Poienii, Valea Iadului and Bratca, which presented favourable economic conditions for the technology of that period.

Following complex studies carried out in the next period by the Geological Institute, a number of remarks were made on the composition of the bauxites and the rocks accompanying the deposit, conclusions that had the effect of improving the technological flow of the aluminium metallurgy in our preparation units.

The bauxites from the Pădurea Craiului Massif are chemically and mineralogically characterized by the constant presence of Al-Fe-Ti elements, whose minerals entirely form them. All these minerals resulted from precipitation processes, hydrothermal metamorphism and alteration, generating existing bauxites.

Among the bauxites in the Pădurea Craiului Massif, the red-cherry bauxites (up to 95%), which are also the main aluminium ore, dominate categorically. The research that led to these conclusions was made in the areas where these bauxites are located, namely: Zece Hotare, Schireaua, Cornet, Brusturi, Brejești, Vîrcorog, Roșia-Albioara, Lunca Sprie and Remeți. It is remarkable that the structure of bauxites varies in their mineralogical composition and colour. Depending on these, the bauxites from the Pădurea Craiului Massif were divided into:

- Primary bauxites to this category fall the bauxites, which have the colour of cherry, red, brown and black;
- Secondary bauxites this category includes red, pink, yellow, white and ash bauxites.

The existence of this ore led to the organization of the exploitation, so in 1963, the "BAUXITA CHISTAG" mining operation was founded, which belonged to the Oradea Mining Trust. In 1965 appears the Dobrești Mining Company, belonging to the Ministry of Mines, being responsible for the exploitation of bauxite in Bihor County, even if it undergoes different name changes, namely in 1990 it becomes MINERAL EXPLOITATION DOBRESTI, then it turns into S.C. BAUXITA MIN. S.A in 1994.

The mining objective of S.C. BAUXITA MIN. Dobrești consists of several perimeters of exploitation and utility groups dispersed on a very wide area, comprising a part of the Borod depression, south of the Cluj-Oradea national road, the Bucea-Aleșd-Țețchea section, a large part of the Pădurea Craiului Massif between Remeți and Vărciorog, extending to the southern alignment Dobrești-Roșia - the dam of Leșu on Valea Iadului. The bauxite exploited in these areas, either through surface or underground operations, was transported to the enrichment stations at Chistag and Dobrești. The bauxite was then transported by rail to the bauxite processing plant in Oradea. This plant was called: S.C. ALOR

S.A. and has as activity profile the production of tabulated alumina and calcined alumina.

The placement of the bauxite resources in the Pădurea Craiului Mountains

The bauxite deposit occupies a territory between Crișul Repede, Crișul Negru, the Dragan River and the Roșia River.

The geographic location of the bauxite deposit in the Pădurea Craiului Mountains, and especially the first three regions are surrounded by railway lines, favouring the operation in good conditions, making the necessary arrangements for transporting funiculars, trucks, etc.

Fig.1 The area with bauxite resources from the Pădurea Craiului Mountains

The bauxite placement mode on the soil profile

The exploitation of bauxite by surface quarries depends on the arrangement and location of the bauxite deposit that differs from one operating area to the other, as well as the depth at which the bauxite is found. As it can also be seen in the adjacent figures, the bauxite deposit in the Pădurea Craiului Mountains, almost in all cases, is confined to the limestone.

Fig.2 The Schireaua bauxite resource diagram (36/64 lens), after V. Papiu
1 – limestone (Jurassic superior); 2- bauxite 3 – limestone; 4 – lehm bauxitifer

Fig. 3 The Cornet bauxite resource diagram, (after V. Papiu)
1 – Jurassic limestone; 2- cherry bauxite; 3 – iron depleted bauxite;
4 – Neocomian brecciated limestone; 5 – massive Neocomian limestone;

2. Methods for bauxite exploiting

The opening concept includes all the mining work in the underground or on the surface, which provides the necessary conditions for the rational and efficient exploitation of the deposits.

Consequently, choosing the optimal solution to open a mining operation is a highly responsible operation. The optimal solution will take into account the complexity of all the acting factors (economic, social and environmental).

The Piatra Craiului Massif has had bauxite reserves that are confined to deep steps. In the first depth step of 0-150 m there are a series of perimeters such as Chicera, Piatra Șoimului, Astileu, Valea Cubleșului, Zece Hotare and Răcaș.

The second stage, where the bauxite reserves are at a depth of 150-350 m, these reserves are located in the perimeters of Remeți, Dealul Măgurilor – Valea Lazuri.

The third step refers to the bauxites located at depths greater than 350 m, comprising the perimeter on the western side of the Pădurea Craiului Massif.

Depending on the depth at which the bauxite ore is located, its exploitation can be done by:

1. Underground exploitation is the work that is being carried out for extracting large-scale ore. In order to establish the correct method of opening, a number of factors influence the choice of the method. The main factors of influence are of geological, technical and economic type.
2. Exploitation of the day or in the quarry is a complex of the works made for the exploitation of the deposits that are at a low depth.

3. Materials and research methods

The quarry covered by the present study is located in Zece Hotare, Bihor County, in the Pădurea Craiului Mountains. A map of land use in this area is shown in Figure 4.1. The exploitation of bauxite ceased in 1998. The surface of the former bauxite quarry is of 10 hectares.

Fig. 4 The land use map in the Vârciorog-Zece Hotare area, Bihor

Fig. 5 Bauxite quarry in Zece Hotare, Bihor County
Surface occupied by the bauxite exploitation quarries from the Pădurea Craiului Mountains

In the case of Dobrești mining, the area occupied by the quarries is of 130,575 m², plus other land that has been set aside either temporarily or permanently, these lands come from the access roads, tailings dumps resulting from underground exploitation, as well as tailings ponds.

Table 1. Surfaces occupied by bauxite quarries managed by S.C. BAUXITA S.A. Dobrești

No.	Exploitation area	Type	No. of quarries	Quarry (m ²)
1.	Cornet	Forest	12	43,273
2.	Roșia-Albioara	Forest	15	84,242
3.	Vărciorog	Forest	1	8,292
4.	Zece Hotare I	Forest	7	12,300
5.	Zece Hotare II	Agricultural	2	2,468
6.	Total	Forest	35	128,107
		Agricultural	2	2,468
7.	Total degraded terrain			130,574

From the bauxite extraction technology results a slurry that is stored in the tailings ponds. The Dobrești Mining Exploitation holds two tailings ponds, namely: the Chistag Tailings Pond is a rib pond located on the major riverbed of Crișul Repede, with a height of 12.5m; the Dobrești decantation pond consists of two bodies, one on the Vasia valley being 14.5 m high and the second one located

on the Vezinoși valley having a height of 32 m and consisting of two compartments. The situation of the areas occupied by the tailings ponds is presented in

Table 2. Surfaces occupied by ponds

No.	Placement area of the ponds	Occupied area (m ²)
	Dobrești ponds	358,493
	Chistag pond	308,890
	The total area occupied by ponds	667,380

4. Results and discussions

The mining operation at Zece Hotare, in its long existence, has affected all environmental factors, which is why the issue of rehabilitation, the use of mining waste for various purposes and the degradation of degraded land in the economic circuit is now very serious. Bauxite deposits are depleted by exploitation only in a few decades, leaving behind surfaces for which man and nature together have to make a common front for their reconstruction.

The ecological rehabilitation of the quarry in Zece Hotare involves the bringing into the economic circuit of degraded land areas through exploitation activities, so it is compulsory to develop re-cultivation technologies. One of the methods that can lead to the restoration of these soils is the generation or regeneration of the soil cover on the areas degraded by the industry which is an original method of re-cultivation, another possibility of restoration being the reproduction in the economic circuit of degraded and polluted lands.

The restoration in the economic circuit of land from mining exploitations means all the work being done to transform these areas into productive areas for agriculture, forestry, fish farming, whose output is comparable to the original results. Re-cultivation of land degraded by mines to date is the action of restitution of useful capacity or production of soils through technical and biological treatments. Re-cultivation implies, at the same time, the use of all means of reducing the surface of the land, affected by the exploitation and liquidation of the damages caused by the degraded soils.

The technical-mining rehabilitation of the quarries from the operation of the bauxite at Zece Hotare requires the passage of some technological stages, namely: levelling the surface of the quarry; fighting erosion in quarries; forest re-cultivation.

1. Land levelling is one of the most important operations in the recovery process. Without proper levelling, uniform soil reproduction cannot be achieved. Depending on the geometry of the quarry, the levelling works must start immediately after the career is stable to work safely.

2. Works to fight soil erosion are part of the measures to prevent erosion, landslides and soil degradation. In quarries, regardless of whether they are on agricultural, pasture or forest land, they require this work, because after the levelling of the land if no action is taken, the erosion occurs.

3. Forest re-cultivation can begin even from the stage of levelling the land. Afforestation is usually done with seedlings of different essences depending on the local silico-climatic conditions and the nature of the pits. Generally, seedlings are planted at distances of 4 m and after about 4 years. If the soil still requires activation and enrichment in humus, then a variety of fast growing and non-planting trees is planted, which will then be replaced with tree species of high economic value. The mature tree transplantation process can be used both in the improved and untreated lands. Some of these works are also valid for the tailing pond where other specific technologies need to be applied.

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REVENUES / EXPENDITURES REPORT AND ITS INFLUENCE ON ROMANIA'S POPULATION FOOD CONSUMPTION

Marian CONSTANTIN¹, Raluca NECULA¹, Iulian DRĂGHICI¹

Abstract. The food consumption of the population is a matter of vital importance, being considered one of the main criteria that determines the ratio of incomes / expenditures of the population (but simultaneously it is a quantitative and qualitative determinant element of the food structure). This paper presents on one hand the situation of food consumption level of the population in Romania and on the other hand a presentation of consumption forms in the dynamics of the period 2011-2017. The structure of the indicators used in the paper is focused on the expression in physical and percentage units (annual comparisons capture variations in the analyzed dynamics). Levels of food consumption are reproduced through the specific varied forms that deepen a correlation relationship. The presentation of correlative forms is based on the knowledge of the interrelation between daily average food consumption and gross domestic product per capita, labor productivity and nominal earnings. Standard averages and deviations are complemented by the coefficient of variation, elasticity, and growth rate. Through the regression equations, the calories consumption level (Y_{ca}) can be ascertained on the basis of changes in Gross Domestic Product ($Y_{caj_1} = 12,77 X_1 + 2950$), labor productivity ($Y_{caj_2} = 5,013 X_2 + 3033$) and Nominal Earning ($Y_{caj_3} = 0,2215 X_3 + 2994$), along with the protein consumption according to the functions (Y_{pa}) that are similarly rendered according to Gross Domestic Product ($Y_{paj_1} = 0,068X_1^2 - 4,1434X_1 + 171,2$), $Y_{paj_2} = 0,012X_2^2 - 1,483X_2 + 153,8$) and Nominal Earning ($Y_{paj_3} = 97,56 X_3 + 0,0072$). The results of the consumption correlations of calories / proteins (Y_c , Y_p) and the influence of each of the influence factors (X_1 , X_2 , X_3) were also presented by the graphic form, resulting in the evolutionary trend. The standard deviation and the coefficient of variation highlight the degree of scattering of the elements and their degree of homogeneity. The structural package and the level of indicators presented underlie the calorie and protein basis, the growth rate of food consumption at national level.

Keywords: food consumption, standard deviation, rhythm of growth, elasticity.

Introduction

On food consumption, it can be said that it is permanently linked directly to the possibilities of the amount of income earned. But it is also found that these food expenditures influence all other non-food expenditure. This paper seeks to highlight through a three-dimensional knowledge system: the annual level and the

¹ University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Bucharest, 59 Mărăști, District 1, 11464, Bucharest, Romania, emails: marianconstantin2014@yahoo.com; raluca_nec@yahoo.com

increasing pace of these consumptions, on the total and by the structure of expenditures (food); the comparison given by the annual levels presented in the dynamics of the years 2011-2017 compared to the base year 2011; substantiation by correlated forms resulting from the regression equations complemented by basic statistical indicators of the variational system. Through the structural analysis of this analysis system focused/exemplified by consumptions in calories and proteins, the elements specific to food consumption were captured precisely through the income/expense report. The comparative level of the current consumption of calories and proteins was highlighted, as well as the specific food consumption trends in Romania. The manifestation of variations in the annual levels of food consumption was given by using appropriate statistical indicators. At the same time, the presentation and the graphical form of the results emerged from the calculation constitute a complement to the knowledge of the socio-economic two-dimensional effect with both income/expense ↔ food consumption.

Materials and methods

In this paper, the form of the methodological criteria was focused on the normative-constructive field, the technical-economic indicators and the appropriate statistic indicators, complemented by the results of the regression functions system. Through these indicators for the dynamics of 2011-2017 have actually been pursued the annual levels for: the physical indicators of consumption represented by calories, proteins, lipiars and carbohydrates; value indicators represented by revenue, earnings, costs, productivity expressed in Lei/household and Lei/employee. The indicators presented by the percentage form have created a basis for comparison both to the annual succession of the period analysed, but also to the first year of this period (2011).

Further, the main indicators of consumption, with reference to calories (Y_{caj}) and proteins (Y_{paj}), were integrated with the main influence factors represented by gross domestic product (X_1), labour productivity (X_2) and nominal earnings (X_3) in regression functions. Based on the annual variation of influence factors (with reference to variables $\pm x$), consumption levels (Y) have been determined by using regression equations/functions ($Y = a + bx$) to determine the adjusted level for the years Analyzed.

By the values derived from the standard deviation calculations and the coefficient of variation, the dispersion of the annual values and the degree of homogeneity was determined, indicating the link between the binding variables (X_1, X_2, X_3) and the consumption of calories (Y_{caj}) and proteins (Y_{paj}). The assessment of the extent of scores spreading around the average was included in the structure of the following steps: values lower than 15% which indicated a low spreading rate, those with values between 15-30% which showed moderate

spreading, and those with a variation over 30% showing a large scatter (in this case the average is not a good indicator of the trend).

The iterative percentage change of a variable that was expressed using elasticity took into account the iterative percentage change of another variable. It was considered a special concept, because in any interpretation about the food consumption of the population, an important role belongs to the factors of influence. Elasticity was expressed by a positive value (an absolute value), thus: if its value is less than 1 it can be said that the variable y through x is inelastic; if the coefficient of elasticity is greater than 1 then y is considered to be elastic with regard to x , since each percentage change of the factor leads to an even greater change in y .

On this basis, the intensity of growth rate and elasticity between calorie consumption (Y_{caj}) and protein (Y_{paj}) and the main factors of influence gross domestic product (X_1), labor productivity (X_2) and nominal earning (X_3) were determined.

At the same time, by drawing up the scenarios, the prospective knowledge of consumption was monitored as a result of variation in the influence factors level ($x \rightarrow \pm 5\% \dots \pm 15\%$).

The methodological form followed, on the one hand, by the interpretations resulting from the level of the presented indicators, respectively the highlighting of the actual situation, the level and the causes of the variation of the calorie and protein consumption, and a further highlighting of the possibilities / presumptive way of developing the researched phenomena.

Results and discussions

The phenomenon analyzed for the period 2011-2017 was repeated in a form appropriate to the problems of general knowledge of consumption and factors of influence. On this basis, according to the uni-factor regression functions and the statistical indicators for the consumption of calories and proteins were analyzed the analytical adjustments that were further substantiated by the statistical indicators.

I. The evolution of the level of consumption and influence factors at national level

Food consumption in Romania through the presentation of the absolute consumption of calories, proteins, carbohydrates and lipids, as well as the level of indicators, permanently implies a deepening of the knowledge of the economic and social factors influencing these human consumption. Table 1 shows this structure by indicators in absolute and percentage terms (by comparison with 2011), which for the period 2011-2017 could be interpreted in a staggering manner in the dynamics mentioned.

a). Consumers' incomes and earnings are differentiated to annual growth rates as compared to 2011. Thus, if the total monthly income per household increases by + 37.0% in 2017, money income, gross monthly and gross nominal earning growth rates for the same reference base are + 55.0%, + 62.7% and + 61.9%, respectively.

b). The monthly labor cost and labor productivity analyzed in the same annual dynamics is represented by increases, but for the last year they are + 56.0% and + 49.1% respectively (2016) respectively.

c). Calories and main nutritional factors concerning the consumption per inhabitant give a delimitation in the levels of consumption per inhabitant in the structure of the analyzed years. Compared to the year 2011, it is found that for the years 2012-2014, this level of calories is lower (these are recorded in values between 96.9% and 97.9%), and in the period 2015-2017 to record increases (the values being between 102.1% and 103.2%). A similar situation is also found for proteins and lipids. With reference to the carbohydrate nutrient factor it is found that the levels of all the years analysed are inferior to the level of the year 2011.

Table 1. Evolution of the level of income, expenditure and food consumption in Romania

Specify	MU	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
Total monthly income per household	Lei Monthly	2,417	2,475	2,559	2,500	2,687	2,945	3,392	
	% versus year 2011	100	102.3	105.8	103.4	111.1	121.8	137.0	
Cash income on a household	Lei Monthly	1,975	2,039	2,137	2,103	2,362	2,633	3,063	
	% versus year 2011	100	103.2	108.2	106.4	119.5	133.3	155.0	
Nominal monthly gross average earnings	Lei/employee per total economy	1,980	2,063	2,163	2,328	2,555	2,809	3,223	
	% versus year 2011	100	104.1	109.2	117.5	129.0	141.8	162.7	
Nominal monthly net average earnings	Lei/employee per total economy	1,444	1,507	1,579	1,697	1,859	2,046	2,338	
	% versus year 2011	100	104.3	109.3	117.5	128.7	141.6	161.9	
Monthly labour cost (total economy)	LEI/employee	2,569	2,675	2,813	2,988	3,189	3,493	4,008	
	% versus year 2011	100	104.1	109.4	116.3	124.1	135.9	156.0	
Labour productivity on a busy person	Lei/person	54,593.8	60,413.9	65,409.5	68,537.9	73,481.8	81,424.1	-	
	% versus year 2011	100	110.6	120.0	125.4	134.6	149.1	-	
Average daily dietary consumption (calorie expression and nutritional factors) per inhabitant	Calories	3390	3,287	3,302	3,321	3,464	3,462	3,500	3,500
		100	96.9	97.4	97.9	102.1	102.2	103.2	103.2
	Protein	110.0	106.6	108.4	108.6	112.3	112.4	114.1	114.1
		100	96.9	98.5	98.7	102.0	102.0	103.7	103.7
	Lipids	104.3	103.6	99.6	106.6	111.7	113.6	116.2	116.2
		100	99.3	95.4	102.2	107.0	108.9	111.4	
	Carbohydrates	481.4	460.8	471.8	460.4	479.9	476.3	477.8	477.8
		100	95.7	98.0	95.6	99.6	98.9	99.2	99.2

Source: INS, Statistical Yearbook of Romania 2018, Bucharest

From the analysis of the evolution of incomes, expenditures and food consumption in dynamics 2011-2017 results differentiated levels and rhythms. For income, wage earnings, monthly cost and labour productivity, a succession of annual increases is recorded, with differentiated levels. For the consumption of calories, proteins and lipids it can be delimited a first period (2012-2014) in which they are below the level of 2011, after which increases exceeding the level of 2011 are recorded. The carbohydrate nutrient factor is every year below the level of the year 2011, but at which a rhythm of growth is found.

Hence, the conclusion that although revenues, earnings, monthly costs and productivity are fraught with a successive annual increase, growth rates are more pronounced than consumption. It is observed that these annual consumption does not align with the other increases of incomes and expenditures, from which it follows that in the analyzed dynamics are noted decreases of the growth rate. Socio-economic factors influence both calorie consumption (as a qualitative factor) and protein, carbohydrate and lipid (considered qualitative factors).

II. The level of calorie consumption as a result of variations in influence factors

Human consumption of calories expresses the main element of comparison in the analysis of the population's standard of living. At the same time, the question of knowledge of the level and influence of influence factors arises. This knowledge was analysed by the interpretative forms of regression functions and statistical indicators presented in table 2.

A). – The adjusted levels of the average daily calorie food consumption (Y_c) result from the regression functions of the influence factors (X) that have been taken into question, with the indication that for each differentiations can be reported. The establishment of linear, unifactorial regression function between gross domestic product, labour productivity, nominal earnings and inflation rate was achieved with the EXCEL spreadsheet program. In this way, it was created the possibility of expressing the evolution of consumption when the influence factors are known (X_1, X_2, X_3). From the analysis of the influence factors nominal earnings (X_3) can be considered with the most significant influence (because the adjusted Y_{caj} values₃ are the highest).

B). – As regards the statistical indicators, the oscillations of the annual consumption level and the variation in the influence factors were particularly discussed. Thus, at an annual average consumption (Y_{caj}) of 3389 kcal are determined values that are differentiated from the average.

▪ the standard deviation with low values for gross domestic product and labor productivity shows that the values are slightly spaced from the average, and the nominal earning by the very high consumption figures shows that the data are distanced, scattered strongly against the average.

▪ The coefficient of variation which is only 2.6% in the case of consumption, for gross domestic product and productivity shall be considered as reduced (less than 15%), and for nominal earnings the situation of a moderate spread (15-30%).

▪ The growth rate (expressed in percentage terms) means an increase in consumption in the dynamics of the influence factors growth (it can be mentioned the increased influence of the labor productivity and the nominal earnings).

▪ Elasticity highlights in the case of consumption that all three factors (X_1 , X_2 , X_3) record a sub unitary coefficient of elasticity ($X_1 = 0.14$, $X_2 = 0.12$, $X_3 = 0.15$). So, from the calculations it has emerged that the changes of all factors influence very little the consumption (elasticity indicates that variable y by x is inelastic). *In an exemplified/explanatory form* for the productivity factor (X_2) the determination of the elasticity coefficient can be given as follows: for perspective based on the year 2017, if the labor productivity will increase by 1% will reach 82.2 thousand lei/ person ($81.42 + 0.81$). By introducing in the equation that refers to productivity ($Y_{caj_2} = 5,013X_2 + 3033$), an elasticity coefficient of 0.12% is delimited.

Table 2. Substantiation through regression functions and statistical indicators of calorie consumption indicators and influence factors

No.	Year/ Indicator	Average daily food consumption	Gross domestic product (X_1)	Labour productivity (X_2)		Nominal earnings (X_3)		
		(Y_c)	Thousand Lei/inhabitant	$Y_{caj_1} = 12,77X_1 + 2950$	Thousand Lei/person	$Y_{caj_2} = 5,013X_2 + 3033$	Lei/ employee Net Month	$Y_{caj_3} = 0,2215X_3 + 2994$
		KCAL (number)		KCAL (number)		KCAL (number)		KCAL (number)
1	2011	3,390	27.9	3,306.2	54.59	3,307	1,444	3,313.8
2	2012	3,287	29.6	3,328.0	60.41	3,336	1,507	3,327.8
3	2013	3,302	31.8	3,356.0	65.41	3,361	1,579	3,343.7
4	2014	3,320	33.6	3,378.7	68.54	3,377	1,697	3,369.9
5	2015	3,464	35.9	3,409.1	73.48	3,401	1,859	3,405.8
6	2016	3,462	38.8	3,445.8	81.42	3,441	2,046	3,447.2
7	2017	3,500	x	X	x	x	2,338	3,511.9
8	Average (KCAL)	3,389	33	X	67	x	1,781	x
9	Standard deviation (kcal)	88	4	X	10	x	322	x
10	Coefficient of variation (%)	2.6	12.3	X	14.1	x	18.1	x
11	Growth rate (%)	0.53	6.83	X	8.32	x	8.36	x
12	Elasticity (%)		39.2	0.14	82.2	0.12	2361	0.15

Source: INS, 2018, Romanian Statistic Yearbook 2017

It follows from this that the levels reported by the level of the statistical indicators for the food consumption in terms of calories, nominal earnings have a significant influence which has a predominant character. This is because the consumer is still predominant in purchasing food products in the situation where the nominal earning increases (it can be mentioned that in the current stage there is a certain behavior shown by the consumer and which expressed in calories shows his degree of satiety).

III. The protein consumption and influence of variation in the main influence factors in food consumption

The consumption of proteins in the current stage of human nutrition is considered one of the most important problems, for which the factors of influence need a particular knowledge. Related to the problem of calorie consumption (as a quantitative side), protein consumption (qualitative side) was analyzed by the same influence factors that structurally was given in table 3. It was sought that through the use of regression functions and statistical indicators to be known the adjusted levels of consumption, which were supplemented by the synthesis of the values of variational level of consumption (Y_c) following the influence of factors (X_1, X_2, X_3).

a). – With the regression functions presented, resulted an adjusted succession of annual protein consumption, but to which the influence factors were known (X_1, X_2, X_3). Effectively, from the analysis of influence factors on consumption it is found that the nominal earning factor (X_3) is most representative because in most years the adjusted Y_{paj3} values are the highest.

b). – The oscillations of the level of protein consumption have been analyzed and given interpretatively from the results of the main statistical indicators resulting from the differentiated values compared to the average.

- Standard deviation of consumption indicates for GDP and labour productivity a small deviation from the average (of 4 thousand lei/person and 10 thousand lei/person, which percentage represents 12.12% and 14.92% respectively), but a sharp distancing of the level of consumption by the influence of nominal earnings (322 LEI/employee net on month representing 18.07% compared with the average).

- The coefficient of variation as a percentage expression frames the influence of GDP and labour productivity at a reduced level of spreading, and in terms of nominal earnings at the range of a scatter class these increases are moderate.

- The growth rate expressing the tendency to increase consumption that compared to the average expresses similar values for the influence of labour productivity and nominal earnings (8.32 and 8.36) and a lower level by the influence of GDP (6.83%).

▪ Elasticity as a level expressed by the coefficient of comparison 1 for the situation of consumption by the influence of the three factors renders a lack of elasticity (values being sub unitary, respectively by $X_1 = 0,41$, $X_2 = 0.36$, $X_3 = 0.15$). As such, the consumption of proteins is very little influenced by these factors.

Table 3. Substantiation through regression functions and statistical indicators of protein consumption indicators and influence factors

	Year/Indicator	Average daily food consumption	Gross domestic product (X_1)		Labour productivity (X_2)		Nominal earnings (X_3)	
		Yp Protein (GR)	Thousand Lei/person	Ypaj ₁ = 0,068X ₁ ²⁻⁴ , 1434X ₁ + 171,2	thousand Lei/person	Ypaj ₂ = 0,012X ₂ ²⁻¹ , 483X ₂ + 153.8	Lei/employee Net Month	Ypaj ₃ = 97,56X ₃ + 0.0072
				Protein (GR)		Protein (GR)		Protein (GR)
1	2011	110	27.9	108.8	54.59	108.98	1,444	108.0
2	2012	106.6	29.6	108.4	60.41	108.45	1,507	108.4
3	2013	108.4	31.8	108.5	65.41	108.65	1,579	108.9
4	2014	108.6	33.6	109.1	68.54	109.08	1,697	109.8
5	2015	112.3	35.9	110.5	73.48	110.24	1,859	110.9
6	2016	112.4	38.8	113.3	81.42	113.35	2,046	112.3
7	2017	114.1	X	X	X	X	2,338	114.4
8	Media (GR)	110	33	X	67	X	1,781	X
9	Standard deviation (GR)	3	4	X	10	X	322	X
10	Coefficient of variation (%)	2.4	12.3	X	14.9	X	18.1	X
11	Growth rate (%)	0.61	6.83	X	8.32	X	8.36	X
12	Elasticity (%)	X	39.2	0.41	82.2	0.36	2,361	0.15

Source: INS, 2018, Romanian Statistical Yearbook 2017

IV. Forecasts of the level of consumption of calories/proteins by influencing the variation of the main influence factors.

The influence of human behaviour on food consumption is in a permanence mobility, which is why the agri-food market must have different levels of consumption. With reference to the consumption of calories and proteins in this work, the consumption scenarios were made based on the variation of the three factors (X_1 , X_2 , X_3) from the regression equations. Variational steps of increase of the three factors (+ 5%, + 10%, + 15%) were based on the last year of the adjusted level of dynamics of the period analyzed.

Table 4. Scenarios on the forecast of calories consumption per inhabitant ($Y_{caj} \rightarrow \text{kcal}$) function of increasing influence factors (X_1, X_2, X_3)

Influence factor	Regression function	Um	Levels resulting from the increase in factor X_1, X_2, X_3		
			5	10	15
$X_1 = \text{GDP}$	$Y_{caj_1} = 12,77X_1 + 2950$	Thousand Lei/Place	40.77	42.71	44.65
	Calorie consumption	KCAL (no.)	3,470.6	3,495.4	3,520.2
		%	0.72	1.44	2.16
$X_2 = \text{Labour productivity}$	$Y_{caj_2} = 5,013X_2 + 3033$	Thousand Lei/pers	85.50	89.57	93.64
	Calorie consumption	KCAL (no.)	3,462	3,482	3,502
		%	0.59	1.19	1.78
$X_3 = \text{nominal earning gain}$	$Y_{caj_3} = 0,2215X_3 + 2994$	LEI/employee	2,454.9	2,571.8	2,688.7
	Calorie consumption	KCAL (no.)	3,537.8	3,563.7	3,589.5
		%	0.74	1.47	2.21

The calculation base is the level of the last year of dynamics ($X \rightarrow$ The value of the years 2016, 2017)

a). – The forecast of calorie consumption was given by the scenarios presented in table 4 to which the level of increases was pursued by the influence of GDP, labor productivity and earning wage. Thus: the consumption of calories per inhabitant records increases in levels between 3,470.6 and 3,520.2 calories per inhabitant, which represents an increase of 2.16% at a GDP gain of 15%; in the case of labour productivity, growth is lower, representing shares between 0.59% and 1.78%; The earning wage can be considered a significant growth factor (the increase is registering for all the highest level scenarios, which also trains the highest percentage levels, which are between 0.74% and 2.21%).

Table 5. Scenarios for protein consumption per inhabitant ($Y_{paj} \rightarrow \text{kcal}$) function of increasing influence factors (X_1, X_2, X_3)

Influence factor	Regression function	MU	Levels resulting from the increase in factor X_1, X_2, X_3		
			5%	10%	15%
$X_1 = \text{GDP}$	$Y_{paj_1} = 0,068X_1^2 - 4,1434X_1 + 171,2$	Thousand Lei Place	40.8	42.7	44.7
	Protein	Gr	115.8	118.8	122.4
		%	2.21	4.88	8.01
$X_2 = \text{Labour productivity}$	$Y_{paj_2} = 0,012X_2^2 - 1,483X_2 + 153,8$	Thousand Lei/pers	85.5	89.6	93.6
	Protein	Gr	115.5	118.1	121.1
		%	1.93	4.21	6.84
$X_3 = \text{nominal earning gain}$	$Y_{paj_3} = 97,56X_3 + 0.0072$	LEI/employee	2,454.9	2,571.8	2,688.7
	Protein	Gr	115.2	116.1	116.9
		%	0.74	1.47	2.21

The calculation base is the level of the last year of dynamics ($X \rightarrow$ The value of the years 2016, 2017)

b). – The scenarios depicted in Table 5 show the results of amplification of the influence factors. It is noted that the highest increases are in the case of GDP growth (the weight being between 2.121% and 8.01%), and in the case of nominal earning growth this increase is the lowest (the weight being between 0.74% and 2.21%).

From this it can be deduced that in the present situation the consumption of calories per inhabitant in the structure of human food appreciated as a quantitative element is possible, even necessary to be amplified because its rhythm under the influence of the nominal earning is the highest. The prospect of protein consumption, which in human nutrition is considered a nutritional factor on the qualitative side, is necessary to increase the increase. This is because the highest weights are recorded in GDP growth and labor productivity, where nominal earning record lower growth rates.

All the problems analyzed relating to the one hand to the fluctuations in the food level and on the other hand to influence factors (with reference to GDP, labour productivity and nominal earnings), a situation that can be synthesised by a form Three-dimensional structural: the dynamics of the main indicators on incomes, earnings, monthly costs and labour productivity through the levels shown in the dynamics give a successive annual growth higher than food consumptions; the consumption of calories, considered a quantitative element, signifies a moderate variation, but whose growth rate is very little influenced by the increase in influence factors; the values of annual protein consumption analysed by annual deviations are found to be forms of moderate increases, a situation due to influence factors that have influenced very little consumption (only for the influence of earning wage is found to be a slight tendency to increase consumption).

Conclusions

The conjectural ensemble regarding the level of the incomes / expenses ratio on the Romanian food consumption can conclude the following:

1.–In the dynamics of the analysed period (2011-2017) there is a definite but differentiated tendency to increase the annual levels of income/expenditure and food consumption indicators. Increases in revenue/expenditure are very much higher (in the succession of the years it can be inferred that in the last year compared to 2011 year, these increases reach percentage values between + 37.0% and + 62.7%). For increases in food consumption, the following can be found: for the consumption of calories, carbohydrates and lipids during the years 2012-2014 a decrease is recorded after which in the period 2015-2017 there are increases (in the last year increases are between + 3.7% and + 11.4%), and for carbohydrates the levels of consumption are located all years 2012-2017 below the limit of 2011 (between 95.7% → 99.2%).

2.–Regarding the human consumption of calories analyzed by the regression functions of influence factors can highlight the influence of nominal earnings (X_3) with the most significant influence. The consumption oscillations highlight differentiated levels compared to the average, which is shown by the values of the standard deviation and the coefficient of variation, eventually an amplification of the growth rhyme can be inferred.

3. – The consumption of proteins analysed by the same influence factors reveals that moderate increases are manifested for annual deviations alongside the same moderate variations, due to influence factors that have influenced very little the consumption (only for the influence of earning is a slight tendency to increase the protein consumption). In the variation of protein consumption the nominal earnings is considered the most representative factor of influence (since in most years the adjusted Y_{paj_3} values are the largest).

4. – The consumption of calories/proteins rendered by scenarios leads to a presumed knowledge of the food consumption of which a continuous mobility is found. The variational steps in regression equations give an increase in calorie consumption under the predominant influence of earning wage and an increase in protein consumption through the predominant growth of GDP and labour productivity, a situation which the nominal earnings record has much lower growth rhythms. All this is because for the consumer there is still a predominant behaviour in the purchase of agri-food products where the nominal salary increases (reference may be made to the fact that in the current stage there is a certain behavior shown by the consumer and expressed in calories is the degree of his satiety).

Hence, the need for a new balance of food security adapted to the national system in Romania, which in the current stage is not proportional to the consumption of calories and nutrients (a phenomenon illustrated by the differentiated rhythms of the annual increases in calories, but also to proteins and carbohydrates).

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